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D8.11-Early warning and spatial Digital Twin Assessment Report

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Interface
ASI	Agenzia Spaziale Italiana (Italian Space Agency)
CC	Coastal City
CCLL	Coastal City Living Lab
CEMS	Copernicus Emergency Mapping Service
COSMO-SkyMed	COntellation of small Satellites for Mediterranean basin Observation
CSK	COSMO-SkyMed
CSG	COSMO-SkyMed (Second Generation)
DB	Database
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DT	Digital Twin
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
EBA	Ecosystem Based Adaptation
EWS	Early Warning Support
Euskalmet	Euskal Meteorologia Agentzia (Weather agency of Basque countries)
GIS	Geographical Information System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IRL	Impact Readiness Level
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KTP	Knowledge Transfer Plan
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
meteo.cat	Servei Meteorològic de Catalunya (weather service of Catalunya)
ML	Machine Learning

OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Project Results
REST	Representational State Transfer
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SIP	SCORE ICT Platform
SIR (Toscana)	Servizio Idrologico della Regione Toscana (Hydrological service of Tuscany region)
SRL	Societal Readiness Level
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
USE	User Scenario Evaluation
WFS	Web Feature Service
WMS	Web Map Service
WMTS	Web Map Tile Service

BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE SCORE PROJECT

SCORE is a four-year EU-funded project aiming to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities.

The intensification of extreme weather events, coastal erosion and sea-level rise are major challenges to be urgently addressed by European coastal cities. The science behind these disruptive phenomena is complex, and advancing climate resilience requires progress in data acquisition, forecasting, and understanding of the potential risks and impacts for real-scenario interventions. The Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) supported by smart technologies has potential to increase climate resilience of European coastal cities; however, it is not yet adequately understood and coordinated at European level.

SCORE outlines a co-creation strategy, developed via a network of 10 coastal city 'living labs' (CCLs), to rapidly, equitably, and sustainably enhance coastal city climate resilience through EBAs and sophisticated digital technologies.

The 10 coastal city living labs involved in the project are: Sligo and Dublin, Ireland; Barcelona/Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm and Basque Country, Spain; Oeiras, Portugal; Massa, Italy; Piran, Slovenia; Gdansk, Poland; Samsun, Turkey.

SCORE will establish an integrated coastal zone management framework for strengthening EBA and smart coastal city policies, creating European leadership in coastal city climate change adaptation in line with The Paris Agreement. It will provide innovative platforms to empower stakeholders' deployment of EBAs to increase climate resilience, business opportunities and financial sustainability of coastal cities.

The SCORE interdisciplinary team consists of 28 world-leading organizations from academia, local authorities, RPOs, and SMEs encompassing a wide range of skills including environmental science and policy, climate modelling, citizen and social science, data management, coastal management and engineering, security, and technological aspects of smart sensing research.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is the deliverable D8.11 of the SCORE project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534. It is a deliverable of the Work Package 8, whose objective is to develop a GIS Based Early Warning Support and Digital Twin (EWS/DT) Platform and deploy it in the SCORE CCLLs to assist governance in collaborative resilience management strategies. Following a co-creation/co-design approach, the design of the system was obtained because of an intense exchange with CCLLs. Later the platform was developed and finally deployed in three CCLLs. The technology development work is described in detail in several SCORE deliverables, whereas the D8.9 "GIS Based Early Warning and Digital Twin Platform deployment report" describes the deployment in forerunners CCLLs for this workpackage, namely Massa, Vilanova i la Geltrù and Oarsoaldea. This D8.11 deliverable is the second one of the Task 8.5 (Assessment of integrated early warning support and spatial digital twin) and involves the partners CNR (leader), LAMMA, MBI, ATU, ERINN, UCD, and the CCLLs through the WP2 partners. It reports how the EWS/DT platform has been assessed at the three frontrunner CCLLs of WP8 Massa, Vilanova i la Geltrù and Oarsoaldea. Assessment activities involve many aspects, such as system performance, evaluation of the physical and AI models adopted, usability and for the EWS component, usefulness with special regards to the regulation framework for early warning management effective at local level, and for the ability to support the co-design of solutions, with particular focus on EBAs, for adaptation to climate change and to improve the resilience of CCLLs with respect to extreme events. It should be noted that the two components of the platform (EWS/DT) have been implemented by sharing the same architectural solutions.

The previous D8.10, released at M24, defined the plan and procedures to be followed for assessing and validating the technologies developed in WP8 and provide guidance to the assessment activities, whereas the deliverable D8.11 contains the results of the validation, scheduled for the end of the project. The assessment methodology will be implemented through different activities that encompass characteristics and expectations of DT and EWS and includes both technical and science validation of the solutions and specific activities to be carried out by the CCLLs. The two products have been implemented by sharing same architectural solutions, but aim at different goals and target different end-users, and different stakeholders as well. Therefore, assessment exercises need to consider such differences.

LINKS WITH OTHER PROJECT ACTIVITIES

The assessment activities carried out within Taks 8.5 aimed at the evaluation of two major outcomes of SCORE, such as the DT and EWS systems. Both are deeply related to most of the technical WPs of SCORE. For this reason, partners involved in technical activities took part in this task.

WP2 has provided interaction to the CCLLs where the DT and EWS systems will be implemented and assessed and facilitated the involvement of citizens and stakeholders in impact assessment.

WP5 has developed the SCORE ICT platform (SIP), developed considering the FAIR data management approach that collects relevant data obtained through the CCLLs making them usable by the DT and EWS systems. WP5. Part of WP5 is the development and continuous update of the data management plan document that explains the procedures followed to manage data according to FAIR principles. Of particular importance are parts concerning ownerships and licensing of data made available at CCLLs and the management of questionnaires and other activities involving interactions with humans, developed in accordance with ethical requirements reported in the "Ethics requirements", deliverable 11.1 of WP11, also included in the different releases of the Data Management Plan Document and updated for the latest version.

WP 3 has dealt with climate projections downscaling tools, modelling and statistical tools and analogous models have been implemented for (or interfaced to) the DT-EWS systems. Finally, WP1 and WP6 have provided mapping of risks at CCLs to be considered for assessment and, WP6, also data to estimate damages at CCs.

WP9 has cooperated with impact assessment. The cooperation was established when Task 8.5 to prepare the DT-EWS assessment methodology and was consolidated in the assessment phase. Important aspects of impact assessment, such as the transfer knowledge processes and viability of the DT-EWS system beyond the project were developed by WP9 and certain aspects are consolidated in WP9 deliverables, particularly D9.3.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The main objective of the SCORE WP8 is to design, develop, implement and assess a GIS-based Digital Twin system and Early warning support system for the SCORE CCLLs and, in general, for the need of coastal cities. In general, a Digital Twin (DT) is defined as a computer program (a virtual representation) that uses real-world data to create simulations that can predict how a product or process will perform if parameters are changed. Instead, the Early Warning Support system (EWS) plays a crucial role in mitigating the impact of extreme events. According to the SCORE workplan, flood risk, associated with storm surge, pluvial or river flooding is considered. EWS aims to detect risky conditions, to reliably predict the onset of a catastrophe before it occurs, and to provide real-time information during an event. EWS has the potential to fulfil multiple roles such as general information systems, decision support systems, and alarm systems for multiple stakeholders including government, private companies, and the general public. Digital twins, beyond the hype effect [R1], are becoming a popular tool for effective urban and territorial planning as testified by recent reviews [R2] and for flood warning and emergency management, as reported by more recent papers [R3] [R4].

The specific DT system developed in SCORE has the objective to support participatory approaches to co-design adaptation solutions, particularly focusing on ecosystem-based ones. The system allows users to run simulations regarding urban weather, *what-if* scenarios or climate long-term scenarios. By providing a quantification of the flooding hazard, it can support technical personnel, policymakers, and citizens as well, in realistically evaluating the impact of adaptation and other possible actions aimed at enhancing the coastal cities' resilience against coastal erosion and extreme events driven by weather conditions, such as floods. The EWS subsystem processes can run continuously, periodically checking the status of environmental parameters collected by an ensemble of sensors (typically run by Institutions) and estimated by different models allowing an all-day monitoring of the flooding risk, raising alerts when some relevant parameters (or combination of parameters) exceed a set threshold.

In general, EWS are supposed to be used by authorized users and are fed by real-time data coming from all the sensors disseminated within the urban area for having a clear description of current weather conditions and for very short-term forecasting (nowcasting), together with weather forecasts provided by local services. The issuing of different levels of warnings or alerts is always supervised and is regulated by national or regional laws that implies specific legal responsibilities for missing alerts or false alarms. However, there are attempts to harmonize warning systems at EU levels and initiatives to promote the early warning concept at global level (e.g., the WMO project Early Warnings For All [R5]). In this respect, the system does not generate alarms for the public, but it is conceived as a support tool that adopts specific interoperability solutions to be integrated with other warning systems. In fact, the SCORE EWS is designed to play a relevant role in supporting the decision-making processes enforced in the different coastal cities to cope with adverse environmental conditions. All the authorities in charge of managing environmental emergencies at some administrative level have at disposal an EWS or, at least, can have at disposal sources from real-time sensors and static data that can be processed or simply visualized to generate warning and alarms with the supervision of a properly trained personnel. Such systems imply a kind of top-down approach for issuing warnings. The effectiveness of the warnings and alarms are in general charged to the efficiency of the characterizing models, for example, precipitation, river discharge, waves, and tides, and to the reliability of the monitoring networks that in general use both in situ measurements and remote sensing. The proposed integrated, GIS based SCORE system using the data and models described above is designed to be key tool to support authorities to promptly adopt measures to reduce the impact of adverse phenomena on coastal cities. Involving citizens through science activities is expected to allow to, on one hand, have at their disposal more observations for a clearer and complete picture of the actual

weather situation and on the other, in a co-warning perspective, it can improve the implementation of measures able to reduce the impact on adverse conditions in the coastal cities [R6][R7].

The DT-EWS prototype was released at the month 26 of the project (August 2023), developed as result of intense co-design and technology development work described in the deliverables D8.1 [R8]. The specification, architecture, user interface, and the achieved demonstrator are described in SCORE D8.2 – GIS Based Early Warning and Digital Twin Platform system architecture and design[R9], SCORE D8.3 – GIS Based Early Warning and Digital Twin Platform Interface Control Document [R10], SCORE D8.4 – Early Warning and Digital Twin Platform prototype[R11], SCORE D8.5 – Early Warning and Digital Twin Platform release notes and user manual [R12] SCORE D8.6 – Tools to access and visualise SCORE data and outcomes [R13], SCORE D8.7 – Tools to access and visualize SCORE data and outcomes release notes [R14], SCORE D8.8 – GIS-Based Early Warning and Digital Twin Platform integration report [R15].

The EWS/DT has been demonstrated for the first time at the CCLLs of Massa in the first semester of 2024 to the environmental managers and civil protection officers of Massa municipality and in successive meetings with the objective of gathering feedback about usability and utility of the deployed version. This was preliminary to aid the deployment in the other frontrunner CCLLs, namely Vilanova i la Geltrù and Oarsoaldea. Then the deployment activities have continued with Vilanova and Oarsoaldea, completed in 2025 (see D8.9 GIS Based Early Warning and Digital Twin Platform deployment report [R16]).

The deliverable D8.10 – Early-Warning and Spatial Digital Twin Assessment Plan [R17] described the methodology to be adopted in Task 8.5 led by CNR (Assessment of integrated early warning support and spatial digital twin) to provide the most comprehensive assessment of the DT-EWS. After the release of D8.5 and the practical availability of a working DT-EWS system the planned assessment activities were implemented, and the present document reports the results of these activities.

The DT-EWS assessment methodology of Task T8.5 was designed through different activities that encompass characteristics and expectations of DT/EWS platform. The two elements of the platform have been implemented by sharing the same architectural solutions, but they aim at different goals and target different end-users and stakeholders. Therefore, assessment exercises need to consider the differences of users and their expected experience.

The assessment methodology was elaborated according to the following 4 activities:

- **Compliance with requirements:** This first assessment activity aims to verify compliance with the requirements elicited at the early stage of the project through interactions with CCLLs consolidated in D8.1 and justify eventual deviations from them.
- **Assessment of modelling used in USE and EWS systems:** Both systems use models: some of them are reused (e.g. the hydraulic model component LISFLOOD FP), but others are being developed within SCORE, namely models based on AI/ML used in EWS. The goal is to verify the ability of the DT systems to simulate realistic output based on available data and on different scenarios built by its end-users (USE) and provide realistic forecasts (EWS). At least it is necessary to demonstrate the reliability of the system in capturing past flood events.
- **Usability assessment:** Usability assessment involves prototyping and iterations with selected end-users according to common practices and standards developed in software engineering. There is a standard definition of usability that has been expanded through the concept of user experience. Systems are designed for usability if they “enable users to achieve goals effectively, efficiently and with satisfaction, taking into account the context of use.” This activity was conducted during the deployment phase and is described mainly in D8.6 [R13], D8.7 [R14], and D8.9 [R16].

- **Impact assessment:** It is expected that both DT and EWS will have impact on co-design practices and in co-warning processes at the SCORE CCLLs. In addition, they are expected to have the potential to be replicated in other European coastal cities outside SCORE. In addition, the perspective on the long-term sustainability of the systems at CCLLs, including their improvements, should be analyzed. Key for impact assessment was the cooperation with WP2, particularly for the collaboration with relevant stakeholders in frontrunners CCLLs were carried out through final online events (held at the beginning of June 2025) devoted to transferring knowledge. The impact assessment was conducted in cooperation with WP9 which focused on the knowledge transfer methodology and developing the knowledge transfer plans for the Early Warning System and Digital Twin (see D9.3- Final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities [R18])

The DT-EWS platform and its performance assessment are the subject of journal articles by CNR and MBI, one, submitted in December 2024 in review in Heliyon¹ and a second one in preparation for the IEEE Internet of Things Journal². The assessment activities were presented and demonstrated at important international conferences (ESA Urban 2024, EGU 2025, ECCA25, Leonardo 2025).

¹ <https://www.cell.com/heliyon/home>

² <https://iee-iotj.org/>

2 THE FRONTRUNNERS

The co-design and co-development of the DT-EWS system has been conducted at the WP8 frontrunners, namely the three coastal cities (CC) of Massa (Italy), Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain), in the Mediterranean Sea, and Oarsoaldea (Spain), in the Atlantic coast (Figure 1(a)). A summary of the main characteristics of the three frontrunners is provided in the following subsections. More detailed information can be found in the SCORE deliverable D1.2 Map and report of climate-change hazards [R18] and in the SCORE geostories³ corresponding to such CC.

Figure 1. a) Locations of the three frontrunners and aerial view of (b) Massa (Tuscany, Italy), (c) Vilanova i la Geltrú (Catalunya, Spain), and (d), Oarsoaldea (Basque Country, Spain)

2.1 Massa (Italy)

Massa (Figure 1 (b)) is a coastal city of 94.1 km² in the Tuscany region with 65.992 residents. The historic center is sited between the foot of the Apuan Alps and the Ligurian Sea, while the area of the city close to the sea is named Marina di Massa. Massa was first mentioned in the 9th century, and its fortune is related to its strategic position in relation to the caves of marble that now are in the municipalities of Massa and the neighboring Carrara. Massa's coastal location has encouraged in 20th century the development of tourism, especially in summer. The city is crossed by the Frigido, a small river originating from the nearby mountains and flowing into the Ligurian Sea. Together with other smaller canals, this river can cause riverine flash floods in case of extreme precipitation or storm surge. Recently extreme rainfall episodes seem to be increasing and have resulted in floods in lowland areas and landslides in the hilly area. Extreme events have hit the city of Massa and/or neighboring cities in the last two decades (e.g. the flood of Carrara on 23 September 2023). . Massa is also facing coastal erosion, which is considered a threat for beach tourism activities.

³ <https://platform.score-eu-project.eu/catalogue/#/?f=geostory>

2.2 Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain)

Vilanova i la Geltrú (Figure 1 (c)) is a city of 70.000 residents inhabiting a surface of 34 km² located on the Mediterranean coast of Catalonia, just 45 km southwest of Barcelona. As the capital of the comarca⁴ of Garraf, Vilanova has evolved from a traditional fishing village into a dynamic urban center that balances its historical roots with modern economic activities. Its coastal location profoundly influences both its economic structure and societal identity. The city is crossed by an intermittent river, like the Torrent de la Piera, that flows into the Balearic Sea, and that can cause damage in case of extreme rain. In general, threats to the local economy, especially tourism and various public services, are climate hazards such as storms, floods, strong winds, heatwaves, and forest fires. These hazards can also heavily impact Garraf, creating damage to cultural heritage, coastal businesses (restaurants, bars, hotels, stores), homes, and two wetlands with their habitats.

2.3 Oarsoaldea (Spain)

Oarsoaldea, Figure 1 (d), is a comarca in Gipuzkoa province, Basque Country, Northern Spain, with a costal extension of 6.5 km and a population of 71.759 inhabitants. It includes several municipalities, with Errenteria, Pasaia, Lezo, and Oiartzun being the most notable. Located along the Bay of Biscay and near the French border, Oarsoaldea coastal and mountainous geography has significantly influenced its economic and societal identity. The small Oiartzun River flows through the comarca, eventually expanding and flowing into the Ria de Pasaia, forming a natural harbor before reaching the Atlantic Ocean. Thanks to this geoformation, Oarsoaldea has been a center of maritime and industrial activity for centuries. The port of Pasaia, protected by a narrow natural inlet, is one of the main commercial ports in northern Spain. The main climate-related hazards identified in Oarsoaldea are storms, coastal and land flooding, and landslides. These hazards mainly impact the tourism sector, residential uses and ecosystems, however cultural heritage, commercial buildings and energy and transport networks are also potentially affected.

⁴ It can be translated as county or district in English

3 OVERVIEW OF THE DT-EWS SYSTEM

In this section, we briefly describe the system's architecture mainly from a functional point of view, exposing the system's structure in terms of processes and interactions with the users.

The SCORE Geographical information system (GIS)-based Early-Warning Support and Digital Twin Platform, that throughout this document will be termed as DT-EWS (digital twin-early warning support) system, is composed of two main subsystems: the User Scenario Evaluation (USE) and the Early-Warning support (EWS). They can run mostly independently, since they respond to different users' needs:

- **The USE subsystem** allows users to perform simulations regarding urban weather, *what-if* scenarios or climate long-term scenarios. By providing a quantification of the flooding hazard, it can support technical figures, policymakers and citizens in evaluating the impact of adaptation measures following ecosystem-based approaches (EBAs) and other possible actions aimed at enhancing the coastal cities resilience against coastal erosion and extreme weather events.
- **The EWS subsystem** processes can run continuously, while periodically checking the actual streamflow, sea state and weather situation depending on available data, allowing an all-day monitoring of the flooding risk, raising alerts when some relevant parameters exceed a set threshold. It will be activated by authorized users and fed by real-time data coming from all the sensors disseminated in the urban area, together with weather forecasts provided by local services.

A description of the architecture of the system was part of D8.4 [R11] and D8.5 [R12]. Some evolution of the system occurred along the deployment phase. More details can be found in Deliverable D8.9 [R16].

The final version of the system will address risks related to flooding from rain and river discharge, as well as the effects of coastal erosion over various timescales. However, the first released version of the DT-EWS system, described and assessed here, does not yet include functionalities related to erosion.

3.1 Architecture

The high-level system architecture is depicted in Figure 1, where the main functional building blocks are reported. The detailed description of the system is reported in D8.2 [R9]. Here we summarize the system's structure and functionalities, which are strictly necessary for a complete understanding of the contents of the present document.

Users interact with the DT-EWS through a front-end Graphical User Interface (GUI) ([R13][R14]) that allows visualization of baseline data consisting of several information layers, such as Digital Surface Model (DSM), sensor location and further layer that a user can add.

The back-end portion of the system includes a database (DB) that stores baseline information specific to the user's coastal city, as well as data associated with user-generated scenarios, such as weather events, sea state conditions, river discharge incidents, and EBAs. Additionally, the database stores outputs generated by the system, allowing users to either view these outputs directly within the GUI or download them to a local repository.

Integration between the front-end and back-end components, and, in general, by different system components, is allowed by Representational State Transfer (REST) Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) (see D8.8 [R15]). They support the retrieval of information from institutional weather forecasts and sensor data or data from external repositories.

Figure 2 Overview of the DT-EWS system architecture and components. GUI: Graphical user interface; DB: Database; USE: User scenario evaluation; API: Application programming interface; EWS: Early warning support.

3.2 Input data

SCORE DT-EWS can handle numerous and diverse inputs originating from various data sources. Some of these inputs are static, others are supplied by users who create simulation scenarios, or additional data derived from sensors. User-provided data can include actual maps as well as hypothetical scenarios, enabling users to evaluate how these scenarios might influence the hydraulic conditions in their coastal cities.

3.2.1 City baseline data

The city baseline data consists of static datasets that can be seamlessly integrated into the system, given their stability over extended periods. These datasets provide the crucial information necessary for the DT-EWS system to perform precise and comprehensive simulations. The results of these simulations are depicted through detailed maps, customized for each coastal city's study area.

Specifically, the system requires:

A Digital Surface Model (DSM) of the city, including nearshore bathymetry. High spatial resolution DSM data are preferred, ideally provided in .shp file format or similar. Maps with grid resolutions of 2m × 2m are optimal for detailed flood modeling but result in increased computational demands. To balance detail with processing efficiency, the implemented system currently uses maps with a 4m × 4m resolution.

A land use and land cover map for the study area, containing essential information on the Manning roughness coefficient and terrain porosity [R20].

Detailed river geometries within the city area, including coordinates of the river centerlines, bed widths, Manning coefficients, and bed elevations.

Exposure and vulnerability maps that SCORE have developed for each of the SCORE CC, including the front-runners. These maps identify critical elements at risk during catastrophic events, such as populations, buildings, and

transportation infrastructures (roads and railway networks). Hence, these maps differentiate exposure of buildings according to their usage and account for associate financial losses caused by extreme events.

3.2.2 Climate and weather wata

Climate datasets are derived from climate models that focus on sea storm surges and river discharges. These datasets encompass historical records from 1956 to 2005, as well as projections based on the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) established by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).

RCPs are climate change scenarios used to project future greenhouse gas concentrations and their impacts on the climate describing different potential trajectories for greenhouse gas concentrations based on varying levels of emissions. The four main RCPs are:

- RCP2.6: A stringent pathway aiming to limit global warming to below 2°C.
- RCP4.5: An intermediate scenario where emissions peak around 2040 and then decline.
- RCP6: Emissions peak around 2080 and then decline.
- RCP8.5: A high-emission scenario where emissions continue to rise throughout the 21st century

The DT-EWS system currently employs data from the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios, representing medium and high-risk levels, respectively, over two distinct 50-year periods: 2015-2065 and 2045-2095. Users can select from various future scenarios characterized by different risk levels and time spans, choosing events with return periods of 5, 25, 50, 100, 200, or 500 years.

Short-term weather forecasts provide typically, with a minimum of 1-day lead time, precipitation intensity, duration, and distribution, river discharge, sea conditions, and storm surge risks. Institutional meteorological services update forecasts every 6 hours or more, and more often in case of risky conditions.

3.2.3 Sensor data

Sensor data are both historical and real time. For the DT-EWS they should include:

- Precipitation intensity, particularly rainfall rate (mm/h), gathered using rain gauges.
- River flow rates (m³/s) or water levels (m).
- Sea condition parameters, specifically:
 - Tide levels (m) recorded by tide gauges.
 - Wave height (m) and period (s) from wave gauges.
- Monitoring parameters from sewage network (where available).

Additionally, weather-parameters (temperature, wind, humidity, pressure) or soil parameters from historical datasets can be used for training the system.

As regards sensor data retrieval via the TERO SensorThings API, the EWS retrieves and processes sensor observations from the SensorThings API⁵. A set of dedicated APIs is employed also to collect the data from the local weather services, in particular:

- Consorzio LaMMA, for Massa
- Meteocat, for Vilanova i la Geltrú

⁵ <https://score.sta.tero.gr/v1.1>

- Euskalmet, for Oarsoaldea.

Updated data about the weather are taken from these services, and employed by the EWS for the flood hazard predictions

3.2.4 Input from users

Users can provide additional inputs for simulations, such as weather and hydrological data. Specifically, when setting up scenarios for what-if simulations, users can introduce data series for weather and hydrological events, either based on user-defined parameters or derived from actual climate and sea-state model projections. Users can define simulation durations and input specific data like rainfall rates (mm/h), average sea-state levels (m), and river discharges (m³/s).

Additionally, users can specify potential solutions based on nature-based solutions or ecosystem-based adaptations (EBAs). EBAs can be selected from predefined lists tailored to each coastal city, allowing users to test these solutions through simulations. Users can specify EBA locations directly on the study area map by creating polygons and are highlighting them. By applying EBAs, users effectively alter land use within these polygons, associating each EBA with distinct Manning coefficients, terrain porosity, and curve numbers. Furthermore, users have the option to adjust terrain elevations before finalizing each polygon, enabling localized modifications to the Digital Surface Model (DSM).

3.3 System output

3.3.1 USE Subsystem Outputs

The USE subsystem generates several maps at different times within the simulation's set time frame. These maps display potential flooding and related water levels in the study area, based on user-defined conditions. Additionally, recalculated financial hazard maps developed through SCORE are produced, showing the estimated damages from simulated events. Upon completion of a simulation, the system creates a human-readable report to help users assess the consistency of the output. This allows users to decide whether to store and analyze the new maps or discard them.

3.3.2 EWS Subsystem Outputs

The EWS subsystem outputs are:

1. **Flooding maps** and associated human and financial damage. These maps are projections based on real-time information from weather forecasts and sensors.
2. **Alerts** for imminent flooding if projected water levels pose risks to inhabitants or cause significant economic damage. Alerts appear on the screen if the user has opened a GUI and can also be sent to designated users via email or other messaging services. This feature can support existing warning systems, with stakeholder discussions planned for future engagement workshops to determine alert recipients.
3. **Warnings** related to data sources, not simulation outcomes or expected risks. The EWS subsystem regularly checks the consistency of received data and warns users if there is a data feed mismatch or inconsistency. Users can then exclude provisionally the problematic sensor from system inputs and plan an in-situ check of the sensor.

Users (end-users) can configure different permissions for the DT and/or EWS. The EWS is an "add-on" feature that can be removed for certain permissions.

4 SUMMARY OF THE ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY

4.1 Planned validation activities and their implementation

The assessment methodology described in D8.10 [R17] was elaborated according to four validation activities described in the following text, which updates the description of the activities with their actual implementation:

- **Compliance with requirements:** This is a first assessment activity aimed at verifying compliance with the requirements elicited at the early stage of the project through interactions with CCLs consolidated in the D8.1 and D8.2 and justify eventual deviations from them.
- **Assessment of modelling used in the DT and EWS systems:** Both sub-systems use models: some of them are reused (the hydraulic model component, Lisflood FP⁶ in particular). Others were developed within SCORE, namely the short-term forecast models based on AI/ML. The USE system must demonstrate its ability to simulate realistic outputs based on available data and various user-defined scenarios; otherwise, the digital twin (DT) is ineffective. This has been done using reconstruction of extreme past events that occurred in the three frontrunner CCLs using data from past flooding events using river discharge data and flood mapping derived from SAR images, which, in our opinion, are the best tools to achieve objectively delineated flooded areas and have been preferred to an analysis of media, reports or claims of damages. The events considered are those with available SAR satellite overpasses. Case selection was conducted in collaboration with the three CCLs to ensure the significance of the events. Additionally, ancillary information, such as damage claim reports, was collected for assessment exercises. The Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS) produces flood maps based on images from SAR, satellites with optical sensors and other sources, but only for important flooding events, namely those affecting large parts of population or economic assets. Episodes impacting cities of the size of the SCORE WP8 front runners are not considered for CEMS processing. Using SAR for flood mapping is based on quite consolidate methods that have proven to be effective, especially in most rural areas. Urban areas, for different reasons, are quite challenging for flood mapping since SAR signatures of some typical urban features, like asphalt, are similar to the SAR signatures of flooded areas and because backscattering from surface is affected by the geometry of buildings (e.g. the double-bounce effect that will be explained later). Urban parks are also challenging because of the signal masking due to crops. Therefore, this validation activity has requested to develop and test a method allowing a good delineation of flooded areas also in urban context. It is recognized that SAR methods based on multiple images (both pre- and post-event) can clarify some ambiguities in the flooded area delineation in urban contexts. Unfortunately, in SCORE WP8 we found cases in which a single image, typically in the post-event phase, was available. Therefore, there was the need to develop a novel method that, using a single, post-flooding SAR image, provides fairly good results also in urban context.

⁶ <https://www.seamlesswave.com/LISFLOOD8.0.html> (last accessed 01/06/2023)

- **Usability assessment:** The usability assessment involves prototyping and iterations with selected end-users according to common practices and standards developed in software engineering. There is a standard definition of usability that has been expanded through the concept of user experience. Systems are designed for usability if they “enable users to achieve goals effectively, efficiently and with satisfaction, taking into account the context of use.” This activity is an iterative one and requires collaboration with users. This activity was conducted during the deployment phase, especially with the Massa frontrunner, namely the pilot front runner, with interactions with users (mainly selected from municipalities or province government offices) and is described mainly in D8.9.
- **Impact assessment:** It is expected that both USE and EWS will have an impact on co-design practices and in co-warning processes at the SCORE CC frontrunners but also in the other SCORE CCs and coastal cities beyond SCORE. A methodology for impact assessment was developed with WP 9. Intense activities at CCLLs were carried out in cooperation with WP2 to involve relevant stakeholders of the front runners CCLLs. Specific sessions have been organized separately with “users”, typically technicians operating at CCLLs and stakeholders, reached through specific session in public or invitation events. A three-step process was followed, corresponding to three interactive meetings (see section 4.3). A questionnaire was used to gather feedback from stakeholders, integrated by summaries of oral discussions. A final online event devoted to transferring knowledge and experience was held at the beginning of June 2025.

The two assessment activities involving people at CCLLs are the Usability and Impact assessment. The following subsection will summarize the activity conducted at the CCLLs.

4.2 Target actors

The assessment methodology of Task T8.5 were designed through different activities that encompass characteristics and expectations of DT-EWS platform. The methodology is described by the deliverable D8.10 [R17]. Note that the two subsystems of the platform, namely USE and EWS, have been implemented by sharing the same architectural solutions, although they aim at different goals, and target different end-users and stakeholders. We consider end-users people interacting directly with the system, e.g. defining scenario, or analysing output.

Therefore, the involved assessment exercises need to consider the differences of end-users and their expected experience.

The USE system aims at:

- Raising the awareness about the importance of adaptation strategies with a tool that support the choice of effective EBAs: facilitating involvement of citizens in citizen science activities.
- Assisting public administrations as policy- and decision-makers in urban planning for more resilient coastal cities against the consequences of erosion and climate changes.

The target end-users of the USE subsystem should include the general public. Concerned citizens could be interested in launching USE simulations to understand the impact of potential EBA on their living environment. However, a minimum training for using the system requested. Therefore, in the validation activities, end-users were found among personnel of public administrations, but also people at associations of citizens or industrialists, willing to exploit, through the user interface, and obtain results of relevant simulations. Users selected for assessment were requested to interact, and eventually guide, the system. Stakeholders, in the assessment exercise, are expected to be in a position for evaluating DT-EWS results and impact rather than its usability.

The EWS system aims at supporting personnel involved in management of emergency or (if they are in charge of it) issuing warnings or alarms with local and spatially detailed short-term forecasts.

Some users, in agreement with the stakeholders and CCLLs authorities, have been appointed and trained to become system operators, thus ensuring the system service continuity and operation also beyond SCORE.

4.3 Involvement of frontrunner CCLLs in assessment activities

4.3.1 Deployment and feedback sessions

Activities concerning deployment and assessment were conducted at the CCLLs following three phases with associated three interactive sessions, involving WP8 team, CCLLs, appointed end-users and stakeholders⁷:

1. System presentation and tutorial

It follows system installation, and the objective is to train selected end-users to “play” with the DT-EWS. Structured interviews were conducted in order to delineate expertise of end-users and to discuss the motivations for the end-users and the organizations they belong to, to use a system like the SCORE DT-EWS.

2. Users’ feedback session

It follows the user training and feedback concerning the usability of the system, and more precise feedback on the value of the system within the organisation(s) end-users belong to. A structured questionnaire is typically used to formally collect users’ feedback.

3. Stakeholders’ presentation and feedback session

After the test phase with designated end-users, the DT-EWS was introduced to stakeholders through public or invitation-only events. From the system developer's perspective, these events serve not only to disseminate SCORE results (the DT-EWS but also results from other workpackages) but also to gather feedback from various groups, including administrations not involved in SCORE, volunteer associations, citizen science groups, activists, business associations, and research and academic institutions outside the CCLL cores. For these stakeholders, the DT-EWS system is expected to provide predictive insights into climate-related risks, highlight vulnerable areas (the USE take advantage from the estimations methods developed in WP6), and a valuable tool support co-creation processes for designing and implementing adaptation measures, with a focus on EBAs. This feedback is also crucial for developing strategies to maintain and enhance the DT-EWS after SCORE.

Although 1. and 2. are more related to technical development and deployment, inclusive of usability testing, feedback more oriented to impact assessment activity was collected since the events associated with 1. In fact, the assessment plan involved primarily a user segment that is mostly focused on CC local governments especially personnel involved in Civil Protection Environment management, city development and environment planning. In fact, most of the selected users belong to specific department of municipalities (or county in the case of Oarsoaldea).

⁷ Note that the process is regarded in the SCORE D9.3 – Final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities [R18], as a two-step from the point of view system exploitation.

It is reasonable to think that interest in the system and motivation to use it is related to the compliance of the system with duties of the user's administrations, such as the obligation to set up a participatory process for long term urban planning or to decide on the change of key infrastructures/land-use, and ultimately the adoption of nature-based solutions and/or EBAs. Such personnel are expected to have a generic ICT awareness (at least familiarity with GIS interfaces) and specific knowledge of procedures enforces ad administration level. Personnel involved in Civil Protection offices are familiar with the different levels of warning/alarms effective in their territory and their duties related to them. For this reason, they are able to evaluate the effectiveness and the usefulness of the possible support obtained by EWS in optimizing the implementation of such procedures. The interest of an administration is supposed to be related to the role such administration plays in the management of emergencies like flooding. Impact could be different if an administration can issue alarms or just implement specific emergency protocol in case of alarm issued. This information on the user's role was gathered through questionnaires or with guided discussion on specific themes.

Similarly, personnel involved in environmental management or city planning are supposed to be aware of the changing climate and the need of adaptation measures. In addition, they are aware of specialistic studies that are conducted during city planning or, for example, the impact assessment mandatory for certain infrastructures. However, the DT-EWS, and the USE subsystem, at the current level of implementation is not an instrument for detailed, executive, design on intervention. Rather, it is expected to promote choice of proper EBAs, favouring the implementation of co-design approaches.

The involved users were asked to fill a questionnaire developed in cooperation with WP9, partner ERINN and WP5 (to be compliant with Ethical requirements and Data Management Plan [R21][R22][R23])

Appendix 1 contains specific questionnaires used by the three frontrunners, which have been adapted to Italian and Spanish languages and sector-specific jargon.

In the following text, parts of the questionnaires are explained and motivated.

Questions about **EWS** were focused on defining the interest in EWS and roles of selected users within the CC administration that could benefit from EW. It is important to clarify the role of end-users and their administration in the context of alert systems and emergency management.

- Which personnel should receive EWS module alert messages?
- In what context might EWS module alert messages arrive?
- Who will be the authorized users to first use and test the system?

Again, on EWS, but related to the time resolution of alarms, whose definition is related to the local hydrological and orographic characteristics and in particular the hydrological response of the region and their catchment basin, or the role of sea waves.

- Every 15', the EWS gives an output as the most probable scenario. If there is at least one in the associated maps where a cell exceeds the alert threshold, the alert is triggered.
 - Does output every 15' minutes cover a sufficiently high frequency?
 - What time horizon may be sufficient (3h, 6h...)?
 - How to establish alarm thresholds? Starting with how many people are affected? As of what magnitude of economic damage?

Still about EWS, an important question concerning user interface refers to representation of alarms of some levels of warning, essential to trigger attention of users:

- If there are areas of the city that require special attention, which areas? Related to what level of (experienced) flooding?
 - Do you prefer the indication of danger bands also known as flood-prone zones (e.g., yellow/orange/red/black alert)?
 - Should the system keep in memory some historical hazard maps, even if the time to which they refer has already passed?

About **USE**: the outputs of the simulations are related to scenarios with and without user selected EBAs (users can select the type of EBAs, the extension and the location, basically modelling the change of land-use). Feedback was collected about the effectiveness and usefulness from officers involved in environmental management and planning, involved in participatory processes, regarding the specific following details:

- At the end of the simulations, the USE module outputs a PDF report summarizing the main data of the simulation and its results. Based on it, the user can determine whether the results obtained can be further studied or discarded. Do users find the report useful? Can you propose system improvements, e.g., further pieces of information that could be added to the report?
- What is the best time interval between the frames in the report?
- At the end of the simulations, the USE module gives output flood and damage maps. Do you think only the final maps are necessary, (i.e., related to the simulation final instant), or also the intermediate ones can be helpful? If yes, with which granularity?

Additional questions are specific to each CC site aiming at gathering information on available sensors and modelling heritage.

4.3.2 Case study selection

Another important role played by frontrunner CCLLs was the selection of the case studies to be used in the evaluation of modelling used in the DT-EWS. As described in sections 6.1 6.2 proof with a sound, evidence-based approach, the ability of the DT-EWS in reproducing the extension of past flooding. This is mandatory for the demonstrate the effectiveness of the system. Therefore, it was important to select impacting events for which a SAR image was present. CCLLs collected also ancillary information concerning the events, such as reports and media and data from sensors. Finally, feedback, also based on informal information to tune to parameters of the system was fundamental to improve the performance of the DT-EWS.

4.3.3 Massa

4.3.3.1 System presentation and tutorial (23 April 2024)

The first deployment DT-EWS was in Massa considered to be the pilot case for SCORE DT-EWS not only for technical aspects, but also for tuning the protocol to interact with users and use their feedback to improve the system. Massa users were identified as the officers working in the department of environment management and in the Department of Civil Protection of the Massa municipality (part of Massa CCLL). The department of environment management deals with long term planning, which in Italy requires, some forms of co-design / participatory approach when significant works are involved, while another department deals with implementing emergency management actions according to a specific protocol. They receive alerts of different severity the Tuscany regional government for hydrogeological emergencies and are requested to implement pre-set emergency protocol.

The meeting was led by MBI and attended (either in person or remotely) by personnel of partners involved in different tasks of the SCORE WP8, namely MBI (responsible of overall DT/EWS activities), CNR (responsible of DT-EWS assessment), UCD (user interface) and the coordinator of Massa CCLL.

The meeting established a format for subsequent meetings with other frontrunners, placing greater emphasis on the development and tuning of the system, as well as its usefulness and anticipated impact (impact assessment). The format includes:

- A presentation describing USE and EWS subsystems, the GUI, the inputs, and examples of simulations
- A live demo of scenario creation that launches a simulation for the system's GUI
- A discussion with the users to collect their first impressions about the DT-EWS system, pose questions with answers that could lead to system fine-tuning, and improve possible impact.

A further training session was held on 09/07/2024, which included a session dedicated to user interface and usability assessment (see Section 7 - Usability assessment).

Additional questions specific to the Massa site aimed at collecting information on available sensors and modelling heritage were included in the questionnaire. Those for Massa CCLL were:

- To our knowledge, the only sensor related to the water level of the Frigido River⁸ is the one at the Canevara station, far upstream from the study area.
- Do you have runoff scales/correlation models that allow you to map, after a known time interval, the value read by that sensor into a level/flow rate value at the point of entry of the Frigid River into the study area? If so, can you make these available to the system?
- Will you install additional level sensors on the minor rivers? If so, will it be possible to receive those data?

The latter is also linked to the availability of data from the WP4 sensors, some of which, in Massa, were aimed at filling the monitoring gaps of the minor hydrological network, being, for the most part, lacking hydrometers.

4.3.3.2 Users' feedback session (20 September 2024)

After leaving some time for the users to get confident with the system, a users' feedback session had been planned for 20/09/2024. During this meeting, the users' comments and observations were collected through the above-mentioned questionnaire. These inputs from the users have been extremely useful for the improvement of systems. Overall, good acceptance of the system has been expressed on the users' side, feedback was generally positive, with some proposals for some system updates.

1. **DT-EWS System Usage:** Massa Municipality officers tried the DT-EWS system and appreciated its interface and logic. It was found usable within their duties, especially for those familiar with similar systems like GIS.
2. **Value and Integration:** The USE system is considered valuable, since similar systems are not in use in Massa. It could be frequently used and integration with the existing monitoring system is feasible at a moderate cost. Having technically skilled personnel and external support are among major threats to the use of the system.

⁸ Frigido is the small river of Massa, originated from the area of marble caves, responsible of flooding episodes.

3. **Support for Planning:** The system supports planning and risk reduction, particularly through EBA simulations, and is seen as more useful with respect to the tools in use, such as reports commissioned to experts and professionals.
4. **Co-Design Approaches:** The system aids in managing co-design events, which are required by law, for example for long-term city planning, though it may increase workload in the preparation of the material for such events.
5. **EWS Impact:** The EWS is seen as less impactful but useful for Civil Protection in post-event activities. However, municipalities would need to manage additional information sources. EWS outputs should be handled by trained specialists due to confidentiality issues and the responsibilities of the officers involved.

4.3.3.3 Stakeholders' presentation and feedback session (28 February 2025)

To collect elements for impact assessment, presentations and interactive discussion at public events organized with support of SCORE, were used.

In Massa, the “*EBA Training School*” three-day SCORE event held in Massa in February 2025, was concluded by a final event in the City Hall, chaired by the Major (Figure 3). The event was organized by the SCORE CCLL core team, and participants included the municipality of Massa (councilor in charge of environment management, personnel from environment management and civil protection offices) that was active in inviting stakeholders, such as volunteers of civil protection networks, environmentalist associations, citizen scientists, teachers and representatives of business associations (note that most cities in Tuscany have a long-term tradition of activism and volunteer associations).

Presentations included a demonstration with illustrations of simulations for the EBAs selected for analysis by the CCLL regarding flood impact mitigation, as well as extensive explanations of the modelling developed in WP3 applied to the city of Massa. Finally, the DT-EWS that was presented through a live demo took place.

The discussion that followed allowed us to verify expectations of stakeholders for a DT-EWS of Massa and to gather interesting feedback, for example on the need to improve the approach to simulate the river Frigido, particularly to better account for the effect of river inundation and the subsequent flush or unwanted transport of 'marmettola', a fine white powder produced during marble rock processing.

4.3.4 Vilanova i la Geltrú

4.3.4.1 System presentation and tutorial (29 November 2024)

The first meeting was organized for system deployment for presenting the DT-EWS to the users of the CCLL and the technical partner of the county on 29/11/2024. The meeting included a system presentation and general overview, followed by a live demo, with a simulation prepared and launched from the GUI.

At the end, a Questions & Answers followed, useful to collect first comments and observations from the users participating to the session. As done in Massa, a list of questions has been prepared and asked to the users, more focused on Vilanova, as reported in the following.

Figure 3 SCORE event in Massa at the end of the SCORE EBA training school. Opening with the mayor of Massa Francesco Persiani (top) and discussion with stakeholders after the presentation of DT-EWS (bottom).

Specific questions for Vilanova were formulated as following, tuned also after the experience of Massa were the following:

- We designed the USE to support administrations in co-design (planificación participativa) with a special focus on Ecosystem-based Adaptations (EBA). For some administrations and projects, co-design is mandatory, while in others it is recommended or not considered at all.
- What is the situation for an administration like Vilanova?
- If your administration has conducted co-design, was it supported by any technology?
- In any case, does SCORE DT-EWS have the potential to support co-design effectively?

- We designed the Early Warning (support) System to help administrations manage early warnings and emergencies related to floods.
- Could you describe the role of your administration in early warning and emergency management?
- If your administration is involved in early warning, what technologies support these efforts?
- Could EWS assist your administration in its early warning or emergency management duties? In other words, do you find it potentially useful?

4.3.4.2 Users' feedback session (13 February 2025)

In Vilanova i la Geltrú, after leaving to the users some time to get familiar with the presented DT-EWS system, a users' feedback session took place on 13/02/2025. In this session the users, represented by a technical employee of the municipality, provided their feedback on the system usability and scope.

1. **Usability and integration:** The digital twin system is user-friendly and easy to use. This was tested after creating scenarios and uploading external data to be shown through the GUI of the system. Integrating monitoring would be crucial for companies in the port area
2. **USE subsystem:** Vilanova City Council is unlikely to use the user scenario evaluation subsystem due to a lack of specialized technical officers but is more appropriate for the comarca government.
3. **Educational Value:** The USE simulation component is extremely valuable for educational purposes and public communication.
4. **Early Warning System:** The most beneficial aspect for Vilanova Municipality is the early warning support system for monitoring hydraulic conditions and assisting the population, maybe through outputs tailored for specific segments, such as schools. Also, in Vilanova i la Geltrú there is a higher territorial administration that provides forecasts and generates alarms and alerts related to meteorological and hydrometeorological risk conditions. The recommendations are considered very generic and not capable of providing detailed indications to the inhabitants or certain categories, such as schools that would need forecasts or nowcasting information presented in an effective way.

4.3.4.3 Stakeholders' presentation and feedback session (22 May 2025)

A one day-long event took place in Vilanova on 22/05/2025, namely the 8th edition of "*Governança del litoral del Garraf: Adaptació al canvi climàtic en zones costaneres: reptes i solucions*". During this event, at which many stakeholders of the city of Vilanova and its surroundings were present, a presentation to the SCORE DT-EWS to a larger audience was carried out, also reporting on some results related to the validation activities for Vilanova. The event included presentations about other SCORE themes, such as experiences on EBAs, distributed sensing / citizen science, with a debate with relevant stakeholders on opportunities for improving the management of coastal areas with focus on beaches.

Figure 4. Event “Governança del litoral del Garraf: Adaptació al canvi climàtic en zones costaneres: reptes i solucions » held in Vilanova i la Geltrú on 22 May 2025. Opening of the Ilolanda Sánchez, Councilor (top). Beginning of DT-EWS demo (bottom)

4.3.5 Oarsoaldea

4.3.5.1 System presentation and tutorial (13 February 2025)

The system presentation for the users, with the tutorial to train them in the system usage, was held on 13 February 2025: the system has been thoroughly showcased to the users, CCLL members and technical partners of Oarsoaldea, along with the needed inputs and outputs, and how to create simulations.

Of course, during this meeting a part has been devoted to discussion with users that have been asked to answer questions. They are the same as the ones asked for in the meetings with the other CCLLs, but more focused on Oarsoaldea, and they are reported in the following. Specific issues for Oarsoaldea were.

- We designed the USE to support administrations in co-design (planificación participativa) with a special focus on Ecosystem-based Adaptation (EBA). For some administrations and projects, co-design is mandatory, while in others it is recommended or not considered at all.
 - What is the situation for an administration like Oarsoaldea?
 - If your administration has conducted co-design, was it supported by any technology?
 - In any case, does DT have the potential to support co-design effectively?
- We designed the Early Warning (support) System (EWS) to help administrations manage early warnings and emergencies related to floods.
 - Could you describe the role of your administration in early warning and emergency management?
 - If your administration is involved in early warning, what technologies support these efforts?
 - Could the EWS assist your administration in its early warning or emergency management duties? In other words, do you find it potentially useful?
- To our knowledge, there is a sensor for the Oiartzun water discharge and level. The data for the discharge (in m³/s) are not available since March 2023.
 - Can these data be made available again?
 - Will you also install sensors on minor rivers? If so, which ones?

4.3.5.2 Users' feedback session (24 March 2025)

After having enabled users to “play” with the system, a feedback session was scheduled for March 24, 2025. During this meeting, users’ comments and observations were collected. Some questionnaires were obtained. Included sustainability technicians, urban ecology coordinators, and a representative from the Oarsoaldea Development Agency. Three operated at the regional level, one at the municipal level, and one from a consultancy.

- **Usability:** The system was considered usable, the GUI being intuitive (minor improvements were suggested for output, like to simplify messages for wider accessibility) and the complexity of the system (from the end-user point of view) is adequate to the goals. This answer came also from users not familiar with instruments like GIS.
- **EWS:** All respondents' municipalities or regions use an Early Warning System, primarily for weather alerts, including marine alerts. They are managed by different agencies.
- **USE:** there are not similar systems in use; others noted regional management of early warning functions by multiple agencies. There was room for use in the administration
- **Value of DT:** The potential of a Digital Twin to significantly improve municipal planning was recognized, being a powerful instrument at disposal of administration to promote climate adaptation strategies. Positive

impacts are on decision-making, more effective city planning. The feedback was overwhelmingly positive, with participants describing the tool as highly promising and valuable.

4.3.5.3 Stakeholder feedback session (30 May 2025)

A specific session for presenting DT-EWS to local stakeholders was held on 30 May 2025 in the Errenteria municipality during a half day event, participated by 12 people in presence and 1 from remote organized with the support of Naider and totally focused on DT-EWS. Participants belonged to SCORE partners (MBI, CNR, Naider), the Oarsoaldea CCLLs, a local institute for marine research and officers in charge development, environmental management and for municipality or for the comarca and a professional consultant. The program included presentation (from remote) of the DT-EWS, live demos, presentation validation of several case studies referred to Oarsoaldea areas, live demos of USE (also with inputs from the users) and a final discussion.

Overall, the system was well received by users, who provided positive feedback and suggestions for future updates, such as displaying more information in the GUI regarding the EBAs. A request was made to MBI for continued support beyond SCORE. The presentation of SCORE DT-EWS included a reanalysis of past events, where inputs were passed to the digital twin, and flooded areas predicted by the DT were compared with those estimated using SAR observations.

Useful discussions were held regarding some features of LISFLOOD FP, used in DT-EWS, while local researchers, more familiar with Hec Ras (used also in score WP3), contributed their insights. Notably, simulations demonstrated the potential of the recently established fluvial park in mitigating riverine flood effects.

Engagement with local experts also provided suggestions on better modeling the ocean's contribution in USE and EWS. In relation to the other CCLLs, significant emphasis was placed on the potential of using DT-EWS in schools to raise awareness among the younger generation about climate change and the importance of adopting appropriate adaptation measures.

Figure 5. The SCORE events to present the DT-EWS system: a view of the room (top) and illustration of a flood map obtained by DT-EWS live demo (30/05/2025)

5 COMPLIANCY WITH REQUIREMENTS

Verifying the system also in a prototypal/version against specification is a key activity of system development. This section reports on the methodologies that will be adopted for the compliance analysis of the current design of the DT-EWS system, with respect to the system requirements and specifications outlined in previous deliverables D8.2 [R9] and also in D8.3 [R10]. It is worth noting that the specifications reported in those two reports represent an evolution of the high-level system architecture sketched in D8.1 [R8] which was brought up to date thanks to the frequent and fruitful interactions inside the SCORE consortium, involving partners with diverse technical expertise and competences and CCLs. Requirements and functional specifications consider the system capabilities of showing different data layers, although some of them are not strictly related to flooding or to the impact of weather and sea state conditions on the coastal cities but are added in the perspective of extending fields of application.

Since the functional specifications are clearly well defined, a straightforward method to check the system compliance is the verification of set specifications against actual implementation. The deliverable SCORE D8.10 – Early-Warning and Spatial Digital Twin Assessment Plan [R17] an evaluation grid. The result of such verification, including comments regarding categories is provided in D8.5 - Early Warning and Digital Twin Platform release notes and user manual (version 1.0) delivered on 31 August 2023 [R12] and is not reported again here.

6 ASSESSMENT OF USE AND EWS

MODELLING CAPABILITIES

Assessing the modelling capabilities of the DT-EWS is essential to guarantee its reliability and usefulness to co-design EBAs interventions and to support early warning alert issues and emergency management. These USE and EWS systems utilize a variety of models to simulate flood scenarios, providing accurate forecasts and facilitating informed decision-making. Assessment was conducted separately for USE and EWS, using a specific approach tailored to each part. This allowed for a more precise evaluation of each part to test the outputs in accordance with their intended application.

On the one hand, the USE subsystem enables users to perform a wide range of simulations, what-if analyses, and long-term climate scenario modelling. By offering a quantitative assessment of flooding extents and hazards, it serves as a decision-support tool to evaluate the effectiveness of various adaptation strategies. These simulations are particularly valuable for enhancing the resilience of coastal cities, helping stakeholders to understand how to mitigate the potential impacts of extreme weather events driven by climate change. The USE subsystem is based on a hydraulic model, LISFLOOD-FP, of which the returned output of the set-up simulations is a georeferenced flood map. A key point of USE is the use of the Manning's roughness coefficient that characterizes single EBAs⁹, whose validation requires the selected EBA to be implemented, as well as the occurrence of an extreme event.

The evaluation of the performance, accuracy, and robustness of the USE system was conducted by reproducing historical flood events and performing a comparison with reference data, namely flood extent maps related to those historical events. The aim of this kind of validation is the evaluation of the flooding spatial agreement between DT-USE flood maps and reference flood maps from the selected historical flood events. The use of sensor-based observational data from the study area enabled the reproduction of the selected historical events, although sometimes, synthetic events were used. To obtain accurate flood maps is not so easy and is particularly challenging for flooding of limited extension, such as those that affected most of the SCORE CCLs. An aiding source could be the damage claim report. For Massa, we have tried to investigate such documents, but they revealed to be quite hard to handle. An objective estimate can be obtained from observations from satellites equipped with Synthetic Aperture Radars (SAR). The method has shortcomings, since not always the revisiting time of satellites allows us to obtain prompt images of the flood. There are well consolidated methods for detection of floods in rural areas, but the application of methods to urban floods is quite problematic (see section 7.1). Therefore, we were forced to investigate the possibility of improving existing techniques to achieve a level of accuracy adequate for testing USE in urban environment, like those of the WP8 SCORE frontrunners CCs. This led to the development and testing of a technique that was used to simulate a flooding event in Tuscany (2 November 2023) that affected the area of Massa but created huge damage in the inland. The method was tested for this flooding event regarding inland Tuscany, since only for this region we had at disposal reference data, such as those from Copernicus Emergency Management Service, which were activate from the critical inland areas of Tuscany and not for the coastal region that include the municipality of Massa.

⁹ https://www.fsl.orst.edu/geowater/FX3/help/1_TOC/Hydraulic_Reference_TOC.htm

The spatial validation of the flood behaviour modelled by DT-USE is a strong basis for the validation of the EWS, built with an ML system. The EWS subsystem operates continuously, periodically assessing the status of the coastal city by monitoring real-time river streamflow, sea conditions, and weather data, depending on availability. This enables continuous round-the-clock monitoring of flood risk and the triggering of alerts when flooding levels exceed predefined thresholds. The key feature of this EWS subsystem lies in its inability to promptly detect risky conditions and issue timely warnings and it is built upon a library of scenarios obtained by the deployment of the USE subsystem. Since the robustness and accuracy of the hydraulic model lying at the core of the USE subsystem were evaluated in the previous step of the validation process, the validation of the EWS was therefore focused on the evaluation of its ability to promptly detect dangerous conditions in terms of flooding and promptly issue warnings. For this purpose, weather and hydraulic conditions of historical intense precipitation events were processed by the EWS subsystem and subsequently its response behaviour was analysed.

The validation of EWS capability is here provided through a probabilistic approach applied to real events occurred in Massa and through synthetic data.

6.1 Using single SAR images for delineating flooded areas in urban contexts

Pluvial and coastal flooding, whose effects are exacerbated by sea level rise and erosion, are major issues that impact European coastal cities like those of SCORE CCs. Like many similar areas in the Mediterranean, they are characterized by the presence of small watersheds and therefore are particularly subjected to flash flooding impacts. Small basins exhibit shorter response times on an hourly scale, occur in more condensed spatial areas and dissipate in less time. Monitoring floods in real time can be complex due to the need for field surveys, especially when a precipitation event is ongoing. In the post-event phase, there are more options to identify floods extension, each one with specific issues. Although alternatives such as Lidar or photograph acquisition from aircraft or unmanned drones exist, using imagery from space is a viable option. Optical imagery from space (e.g. from NASA's Landsat or MODIS sensors, or ESA's Sentinel-2) is a straightforward way to classify water bodies and map flooded areas [R24][R25]. Unfortunately, the potential of optical satellite images is often constrained by persistent cloud cover during flood events and particularly in small to medium-size basins, where floods often recede before weather conditions clear, as frequently observed in Europe. A preferred method for obtaining such maps is using Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images [R26][R27][R28][R29]. SARs are active microwave devices that provide data in almost any weather, though X-band SARs can be affected by precipitation [R30][R31]. A two-dimensional SAR image shows backscattering from surfaces, with intensity (strength of the returned signal) represented by the surface backscattering coefficient, σ_0 . Calm water typically shows a low radar return, appearing dark due to specular scattering.

Rough surfaces scatter radar signals in multiple directions, resulting in a higher power at the receiving antenna, while backscatter decreases for wet terrain, resulting in dark spots in SAR images, making them effective for detecting flooded areas. Urban areas pose challenges [R32][R33] due to smooth, dark surfaces like asphalt, which return low backscattered power similar to water. A common method identifies areas with increased backscatter intensity due to the double-bounce effect and multipath echoes from nearby walls and roads. Flooded paved areas show stronger backscatter because of double-bounce scattering between the sensor, road, and walls. Specifically, double-bounce backscattering is a key scattering phenomenon exploited in the analysis of flood events where buildings remain partially exposed above the floodwater, as observed during the events affecting the CCLLs. This scattering effect arises when the radar signal undergoes successive reflections, first from the water-covered road surface and subsequently from the vertical building facades. The presence of the double-bounce scattering effect is examined

through the analysis of SAR imagery acquired in different polarimetric configurations, in particular co- and cross-polarizations. To address under-detection from intensity data alone, InSAR coherence, which measures the correlation between two SAR images, is used. This technique requires two SAR images from the same orbit taken at different times. Floodwater presence decreases coherence between the pre and post SAR images [R32].

Most urban flood mapping methods are rule-based, including fuzzy-logic [R34], region growing decision trees [R35], and thresholding [R36]. For analysis, machine learning methods ([R37][R38] and references therein), are gaining attraction.

Operationally, the presence of compatible pre-flood SAR images can be improved by SAR constellations, such as the Sentinel-1 satellites, but their 12-day cycle limits flash flood detection (that in many coastal cities, especially in Mediterranean generally occurs within a time interval of the order several hours. The COSMO-SkyMed constellation, with X-band SAR, is effective for flood mapping [R39] due to the higher revisit time (claimed up to six hours in case of full constellation operational), opposite to satellite images when floods often recede being captured due to low revisit time. Multitemporal SAR image methods are consolidated [R40][R32], but single SAR images are often used due to availability constraints.

The Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS) of the European Commission leverages satellite imagery, including SAR and optical sensors, for flood mapping during emergencies [R41]. This service, activated by authorized users, provides reference flood images for the EU and internationally. Since 2013, it has been activated for 37 flood events in Italy, fewer than the actual occurrences of floods. While it can be activated in the preparedness phase, it often misses the initial stages of flooding and usually it is not activated for minor events since the latter are supposed not to impact significantly people, assets, or the environment. Smaller-scale events in regions like the Mediterranean Basin are particularly challenging due to data limitations.

Examining flash floods in small watersheds often relies on a single SAR image due to the limitations of multitemporal images. We developed a method using a single SAR image, focusing on urban areas to create accurate flood maps despite limited validation data. This method was tested on a severe flood in Tuscany, Italy, in 2023, using high-resolution SAR images from COSMO-SkyMed.

The method combines ISODATA clustering [R42] with fuzzy logic, adapting methods originally applied to rural areas, for urban environments by leveraging the double-bounce backscattering effect.

The main steps of the method are [R43] :

- **ISODATA classification and post-classification operations.** The aim is to identify the areas detected by SAR with the lowest and highest values of backscattering coefficients. In particular, the behavior of the backscattering coefficient is analyzed to detect specular scattering in rural areas and double-bounce scattering in urban areas.
- **Computation of average backscattering coefficient** in objects returned by the previous ISODATA classification and post-classification operations. These objects belong to the classes with the lowest values of backscattering coefficients for the flood detection in rural areas and the class with the highest values of backscattering coefficients for the flood detection in urban areas.
- **Fuzzy logic method to finalize the classification process** regarding the heterogeneity of objects within the same class and their geographical location by the integration of river network ancillary data.

To verify the reliability of the DT-USE outputs, a pixel-by-pixel validation was performed by comparing, for a set of historical flood events, the simulated flood maps produced by USE with reference maps derived from SAR images processing.

In the pixel-by-pixel comparison between the DT-USE predictions and the reference flood map obtained through SAR image processing, both datasets are binary, with each pixel assigned a value of 1 (wet) or 0 (dry). Thus, each pixel is represented by a value of 1 (wet) or 0 (dry). Based on this binary classification, the contingency table is constructed computed to summarize the frequency of each possible combination of wet and dry classifications from the two flood maps.

Four validation parameters, based on the relative pixel counts in the contingency table, are computed to verify the accuracy of the DT-USE flood prediction [R44]:

- **Coefficient of Fit Agreement (F):** This metric accounts for both overpredictions and underpredictions, with values ranging from 0 (no agreement between DT-USE and SAR data) to 1 (perfect agreement).
- **Hit Rate (H):** This coefficient measures the accuracy in detecting flooded areas and reflects the model's tendency to miss actual floods. A value of 0 indicates none of the flooded areas in the SAR data were detected by DT-USE, while a value of 1 stands for perfect detection.
- **False Alarm Ratio (FA):** This metric represents the rate of false positives, indicating the proportion of pixels labeled as flooded by DT-USE but not confirmed by the SAR-derived reference data. It assumes values from 0 (no false alarms) to 1 (all predictions are false alarms), indicating overestimation.
- **Error Bias (E):** This coefficient assesses whether the model tends to overestimate or underestimate flood extents. An E value of 1 indicates no bias; values between 0 and 1 indicate underprediction, and values greater than 1 indicate overprediction.

To ensure accurate validation, permanent water bodies (such as lakes and rivers), wetlands, irrigation canals, and water features in agricultural or nursery areas were excluded from both the SAR reference map and the DT-USE output. This approach limits the evaluation to flooded areas only.

The study conducted for the event in Tuscany is described in a paper under review [R43] and demonstrates that results from a single SAR image can be comparable to those from multi-source services like CEMS, useful for validation when CEMS is not activated. The lack of critical observations in the early stages of flood events remains a challenge, as seen in the Tuscany case, where the first SAR image for the area of Prato was available on November 5, while floods began on November 2. According to the LaMMA Consortium reports [R45][R46], on the afternoon of 2 November 2023, a line of stationary atmospheric instability ahead of a cold front triggered the development of several prefrontal thunderstorms. From mid-afternoon onward, strong southerly winds sweeping across the southern parts of the region met with south-south-west south-west winds, gradually advancing over the northern Ligurian Sea. This convergence of winds, combined with the arrival of moderately cooler air at higher altitudes and other favorable storm conditions, resulted in the formation of a nearly stationary storm line that persisted until evening, provoking the flood in the Florence-Prato-Pistoia (FPP) plain.

The analysis focuses on the flood event from 2 to 5 November 2023, triggered by a major weather event affecting most of Italy. The study area is the Florence-Prato-Pistoia plain in central Tuscany. The eastern part includes Florence, the center is Prato, and the west is Pistoia. The storm line caused 130-170 mm of precipitation in 5-6 hours in Pistoia and Prato. Another storm hit on 4-5 November, bringing widespread precipitation. The floods caused significant damage, with rivers and channels overflowing, leading to evacuations and casualties. Civil Protection teams conducted rescue operations. Around 300 people were evacuated, and infrastructure was heavily impacted. The total damage in Tuscany was estimated at 1.89 billion Euros, including 588 million Euros for families and 1.2 billion Euros for businesses. Floodwater from the Bisenzio River and its tributaries caused severe flooding in Prato, Florence, and Pistoia.

The two SAR images used for the analysis of the FPP event were provided by the COSMO-SkyMed mission of the Italian Space Agency (ASI) that consists in a constellation of satellites, equipped with synthetic aperture radars (SARs) operating at X-band (9.6 GHz). COSMO-SkyMed SARs are multi-mode and programmable instruments, and parameters and mode of observation are set according to requests of specific users. COSMO-SkyMed first generation (CSK), including four satellites launched between 2007 and 2010, and COSMO-SkyMed Second Generation (CSG), which consists of two SAR satellites launched in 2019. Now the COSMO-SkyMed constellation is composed currently of five operational radar satellites in orbit (3 first generation and 2 of the second generation).

The available images used for the FPP event analysis were acquired by the first CSG satellite on 5 November 2023 in STRIPMAP mode and dual polarization HH-HV and by the CSK-1 satellite on 6 November 2023 in HIMAGE mode and HH polarization (Table 1).

Table 1. COSMO-SkyMed images available for mapping the flood of Florence-Prato- Pistoia plain occurred in November 2023.

Satellite	Mission Time (UTC)	Mode	Polarization	Resolution [m]
CSG	2023-11-05 17:56	STRIPMAP	HH, HV	1.25
CSK	2023-11-06 05:04	HIMAGE	HH	2.5

The flood extent map from Copernicus EMS Rapid Mapping¹⁰ was used to validate our procedure, specifically focusing on the FPP area. CEMS, managed by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre, supports emergency responses for various disasters, including meteorological and geophysical hazards. It aids in prevention, preparation, response, and recovery efforts.

Rapid Mapping for Emergency Response provides geospatial information quickly (within hours to days) to assist emergency operations. This involves rapid acquisition, processing, and analysis of satellite imagery and other geospatial data. CEMS was activated on 3 November 2023 at 03:21 UTC and monitored the event in Tuscany until 8 November. Figure 6 6 shows the area considered by CEMS in relation to Massa, shown in the box on the top-right corner.

The flood extent map for the FPP event is a Delineation Product (DEL) derived from the analysis of the CSK image taken on 6 November 2023, using a pre-event Sentinel-2 image from 17 July 2023 (a multi-temporal image approach), somehow mapped to a common grid, as the background, along with the Digital Elevation Hydrological Model of Tuscany. It should be noted that Sentinel 2 pre-event image was collected with a SAR using a different band from CSK and with different incidence angle.

¹⁰ <https://mapping.emergency.copernicus.eu/activations/EMSR705/>

Figure 6. The area of the Florence-Prato-Pistoia plain considered by CEMS. Shown in the top right corner is the location of the FPP area with respect to Italy and the Massa SCORE CC

Figure 7. Comparison of flooded area obtained by CEMS (magenta) and our method (cyan) Our method appears as superimposed to CEMS. Differences are better highlighted by Table 2.

Comparison between delineation of CEMS and our method for the image of November 6 are shown in both Figure 7 and Table 2. The analysis returns hit rate H values between 0.89 and 0.93 in the 5 areas, with an average value of 0.90. The coefficient of fit agreement varies between 0.61 and 0.74 with an average value of 0.69. False alarms are in the range 0.22-0.34 with an average value of 0.26, whereas error bias E varies between 2.50 and 4.44 with an average value of 3.42 for all the considered areas. Such values were also compared with other reference techniques (ISODATA and Otsu's methods) that proved worse results.

The delineation obtained by our method have been published to Zenodo among SCORE datasets¹¹, while CEMS data are available from CEMS website.

Notoriously, the lack of reference data is a major problem in assessing SAR delineation methods. However, the fairly good results obtained with the comparison with CEMS, although based on a single image, enable us to apply the technique to the events predicted by the DT-EWS, but for which SAR images are available, but CEMS was not

¹¹ Carlini, B., Paranunzio, R., & Baldini, L. (2024). Flood maps of Rainfall Event of November 2023 in Tuscany, Italy [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14260543>

activated because of the local nature of the events (note that this is a quite common situation concerning floods in Mediterranean and in many European CCs).

Table 2 Values of parameters F , H , FA and E in Areas 1-5 indicated in Figure 9 of the FPP plain.

Area ID	F	H	FA	E
1	0.69	0.89	0.24	.54
2	0.74	0.93	0.22	3.71
3	0.69	0.91	0.26	3.44
4	0.61	0.89	0.34	4.44
5	0.71	0.90	0.23	2.95

6.2 Flood maps validation in frontrunners CCLs

The following subsections report results obtained by comparing the output of flood mapping obtained by SCORE DT-EWS and flood mapping obtained from SAR observations of the same events. The SAR flood maps are available on Zenodo.org¹².

6.2.1 Marina di Massa: flood event of 03 November 2023

The event analysed for the DT-USE validation in the Marina di Massa CCLL occurred on 3 November 2023 and is part of the events that affected a significant part of Tuscany region from 2 to 5 November shown in the previous section concerning the most hit part, namely the FPP plain. Within the Massa municipality, Marina di Massa was impacted by a severe storm surge, resulting in damage to coastal structures and beachfront areas. The flood detection method described above has been applied to this historical event. The available SAR image was provided by the first COSMO-SkyMed Second Generation (CSG) satellite on 3 November 2023 (UTC 17:20) in STRIPMAP mode and dual polarization HH-HV. The flood map is displayed in pink in Figure 8. The DT-USE scenario of the 03 November 2023 event was generated using precipitation and river discharge time series data for the Frigido River, provided by the SIR Toscana service, with the resulting flood map shown in light blue in Figure 8. It should be noted that, due to the unavailability of sea state time series data for the area of interest, the scenario was configured according to a Historical (1956-2005) series with 100 years return period (RP) based on ALADIN63 RCM provided by the EURO-CORDEX experiment time [R47]. The validation method has been employed around the area of interest outlined in black in Figure 8 and the values of the validation parameters are displayed in Table 3. The pixel-level comparison between the two flood maps demonstrated a good spatial correspondence, with the FA coefficient indicating a low rate of false positives.

¹² Carlini, B., Paranunzio, R., & Baldini, L. (2025). D8.11 Flood maps obtained from SAR images processing for historical flood events in CCLs (Marina di Massa - Tuscany Italy, Vilanova i La Geltrú - Catalunya Spain, Oarsoaldea - Basque Country Spain) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15771629>

Nonetheless, a slight underestimation was noted in the beach area (as indicated by the value of E), presumably caused by the absence of actual sea state data. In densely urbanized areas, SAR image analysis enables the identification of flooded areas or areas where water has accumulated; however, a pixel-level accuracy remains a challenging result. Despite this limitation, it has been confirmed that the areas detected as flooded in the SAR-derived flood map also appear as flooded in the DT-USE output flood map. Considering the fundamental differences underlying the flood detection method from the SAR images and DT-USE simulations, the validation results demonstrate a good predictive capability of the DT system model.

Figure 8. Comparison of DT-USE flood map, shown in blue light color, and SAR image-based flood map, shown in pink color, on 3 November 2023 event in Marina di Massa CCLL (bounded by a black line).

Table 3 Values of validation parameters F , H , FA and E estimated using the pixel by pixel comparison of DT-USE flood map and flood map obtained by SAR image for the Marina di Massa case.

CCLL	Event date	F	H	FA	E
Marina di Massa, Italy	03-11-2023	0.49	0.56	0.21	0.34

6.2.2 Vilanova i la Geltrù - Susceptibility assessment

The city of Vilanova i la Geltrù has historically been affected by coastal flooding. Moreover, specific areas have proven to be more vulnerable to flood events. Among these, the areas adjacent to underpasses along the city's main roads are subject to recurrent inundation during events of intense rainfall. Through a review of local news archives,

supported by the municipal authorities, several flooding events that affected the CCLL over the past decade have been identified. These events are listed below:

- 12 August 2019: flooding occurred in the coastal, rural, and in the most vulnerable areas of the urban zone.
- 22 January 2020: flooding predominantly impacted the coastal region; however, rural zones were also examined as part of the study.
- 30-31 March 2024: flooding predominantly impacted the coastal region; however, rural zones were also examined as part of the study.
- 8 September 2024: flooding occurred in the coastal, rural, and in the most vulnerable areas of the urban zone.

Sentinel-1 SAR Images are provided as SENTINEL-1 Interferometric Wide Swath Level 1 (S for Sentinel 1-A images) Product. They have been processed using the SNAP software according to the procedure indicated by ESA¹³ to obtain a raster map of the value of the backscattering coefficient. By using pre- and post-event Sentinel-1 SAR imagery [R41], the flood mapping procedure described in Section 7.1 has been applied and flood maps for these historical events have been obtained.

The validation performed for the CC of Vilanova i la Geltrù differs from the approach outlined above. In the study area of Vilanova i la Geltrù, no hydrometers are available and for this reason, it was not possible to carry out a simulation of a historical flooding event that affected the city and apply a pixel-by-pixel validation. As a result, it was decided to carry out a study to verify that the DT-USE is able to identify the areas of the city most susceptible to flooding events. The event of 08 September 2024 was selected for this purpose. An intense precipitation event caused the flooding in the city area and a tidal wave affected the coastal area. The real time series of rainfall intensity, provided by MeteoCat, was used.

The scenario was configured according to a historical (1956-2005) series with 5 years return period for the river discharge and the sea states. The flood detection method from SAR images described above has been applied to this historical event. The available SAR image was provided by Sentinel-1 mission on 8 September 2024 (UTC 17:55) in the dual polarization HH-HV. Figure 9 shows the flood map returned by the DT-USE in blue and the flood map obtained from the SAR image in pink. The CCLL study area is outlined with a black line. The red boxes indicate areas that have been identified by both DT-USE and SAR image processing as being affected by flooding. In the coastal area, both Platja de Sant Cristòfol and Platja de Ribes Roges were hit by the storm surge. In the city area, the areas adjacent to the underpasses of Ronda Europa (near Torrent de la Piera) and Carrer de Josep Coroleu were flooded. Also, around La Collada, some flooded areas have been detected.

Despite the relatively low resolution of the Sentinel-1 SAR imagery and the absence of river discharge time-series data for the study area, this test case provided valuable insights. Despite the infeasibility to carry out a quantitative validation, it allowed us to assess the performance of the DT- EWS in the Vilanova i la Geltrù area, demonstrating its capability to accurately predict which areas are most susceptible to flooding during intense rainfall events.

¹³ Error! Reference source not found.

Figure 9. Comparison of DT-USE flood map, shown in blue light color, and SAR image-based flood map, shown in pink color, for the 8 September 2024 event in Vilanova i la Geltrú CC (bounded by a black line).

6.2.3 Oarsoaldea: flood event of 19 May 2019

The event analysed for the DT-USE validation in the Oarsoaldea CCLL occurred on 19 May 2019. The local news reported that an intense precipitation event caused the flooding of some roads in Erreterria, resulting in roadblocks. For this event, the available SAR image¹⁴ used was captured by Copernicus Sentinel-1 B (08:58:03 Local Time).

Sentinel-1 SAR Image is provided as SENTINEL-1 Interferometric Wide Swath Level 1 Product. It has been processed using the SNAP software according to the procedure indicated by ESA¹⁵ to obtain a raster map of the value of the backscattering coefficient. The use of the pre-event SAR image provided has been integrated into the flood mapping method described in Section 7.1. The flood map is shown in pink in Figure 9. The DT-USE scenario of the 19 May 2019 event was generated using precipitation and river discharge time series data for the Oiartzun River, provided by the municipality of Oarsoaldea, with the resulting flood map shown in light blue in Figure 10. It should be noted that, due to the configuration of DT-USE sea state setting, the temporal evolution of sea state was defined by a triangular hydrograph with peak value obtained from real tidal and sea level data provided by Puertos del Estado (Spain).

¹⁴ S1B_IW_GRDH_1SDV_20190124T061622_20190124T061647_014632_01B450_A642

¹⁵ https://step.esa.int/docs/tutorials/tutorial_s1floodmapping.pdf

Figure 100. Comparison of DT-USE flood map, shown in blue light color, and SAR image-based flood map, shown in pink color, for the 19 May 2019 event in Oarsoaldea CC (bounded by a black line).

The validation analysis for this CCLL posed several challenges. The complexity of the local morphology presented significant difficulties for hydraulic modeling, which forms the basis of DT-USE. The Oiartzun river stretches 16.5 km flowing from the Bianditz and Aiako Harria mountains to Pasaia Bay with a drainage basin of 85 km² [R49]. In particular, the study area modelled by the DT-USE focuses on the areas of Errenteria and Pasaia. These areas, particularly the city of Errenteria, are densely urbanized, resulting in a dense urban grid. The river flows through this urban landscape and ultimately reaches Pasaia Bay. Unlike the study areas that have interested Marina di Massa (Italy) and Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain), where the port and the coastal area overlook the sea directly, here the port is not built directly on the Atlantic Ocean, but it is connected to it by a cove made up of rock elements of considerable height. In addition, in the port area, there is no bathing area that is free of infrastructure or pavement (e.g. asphalt). This combination leads to challenging soil drainage behavior, complicating both hydraulic modeling and satellite flood mapping efforts. The SAR image available for this study was provided by the Copernicus constellation Sentinel-1, with a significantly lower resolution than the SAR image acquired from COSMO-SkyMed. With a pixel size of approximately 10 m, the Sentinel-1 image lacked the precision necessary to match the flood mapping capabilities of the DT-USE. The narrow city streets of the areas of Errenteria and Pasaia posed difficulties for accurate flood mapping using SAR Imagery. As a result, the validation coefficients (shown in Table 4) were less favorable than those observed during the validation of the Marina di Massa event. Notably, a high number of false alarms (FA) were detected, and an underprediction trend was evident, as indicated by coefficients E, F, and H. The chosen validation procedure, namely pixel-by-pixel validation as defined in Section 7.1, was not suitable for the validation of this area of study. Despite this, it was observed that in the port region, areas identified as wet by the DT-USE largely corresponded to those identified as flooded by SAR-based flood mapping—though not at a pixel-level accuracy. The same trend is observed in Pasaia. For this reason, a statistical areal validation procedure would be more appropriate for the study area of Oarsoaldea CCLL. This method would focus on the overall distribution of wet and dry pixels within defined areas ([R50][R51]). The greatest discrepancies between the two flood maps are detected in the urban area near the river

in Errenteria. The DT-USE was able to predict the expansion of the floodable park (which was not detectable in the SAR image due to tree cover, as shown in Figure 10) but failed to capture the critical flood-prone area of Errenteria near the river. To address this issue, a further calibration phase of the DT-USE hydraulic model will be undertaken for this specific area.

Table 4 Values of validation parameters F, H, FA and E estimated using the pixel-by-pixel comparison of DT-USE flood map and flood map obtained by SAR image for the Oarsoaldea case

CCLL	Event date	F	H	FA	E
Oarsoaldea, Basque Country (Spain)	19-05-2019	0.15	0.21	0.63	0.44

6.3 EWS validation

A key aspect of the Early Warning Support System (EWS) lies in its capability to detect hazardous or risky hydraulic conditions and issue timely and reliable warnings. The EWS System is essentially conceived for minimizing damage and ensuring the safety of people and property in vulnerable areas. The primary objective of the validation process is to rigorously assess the EWS System's performance under a range of intense weather scenarios. Specifically, the goal is to verify that in situations involving intense or prolonged precipitation, river flood events, or localized flooding, the EWS can accurately analyse environmental data from in-place sensors and trigger an early alarm. The primary objective of the validation is not to assess how long the alert remains active, but to ensure that it is issued early enough to precede the most critical phase of the examined historical event.

The concept underlying the DT-EWS is briefly recalled here to frame the validation process. DT classifier determines the probability that a given "current" scenario belongs to a set of predefined "base" scenarios. It first aligns the time series data of the current scenario with each base scenario after scaling. Then, for each element in the scenarios, it uses a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) [R52] to calculate the likelihood that the current scenario's element matches the distribution of that element across the base scenarios. This process generates probabilistic outputs, providing a set of probabilities, where each probability represents the likelihood of the current scenario matching a specific base scenario. From a Machine Learning perspective, whether data of the current scenario is real or synthetically generated makes no difference to a statistical model, given that the model only sees the statistical properties of the data: its distribution, the relationships between variables, and the inherent noise.

Based on these statements, the validation process steps to test the warning capability of the EWS System are:

- **Identification of available sensors** in the study area and the collection of a time series of environmental parameters (e.g., rainfall intensity and river water level).
- **Processing of environmental data.**
 - Rainfall intensity. A conversion of the units of measurement is typically performed to ensure compatibility of input.
 - River water level. The water level time series are converted into flow values using outflow rating curves supplied by local agencies. It was then necessary to apply a spatial rescaling based on the extension of the river basins to adjust the flow time series. In fact, the location of the hydrometer typically does not coincide with the location where the hydraulic model underlying the DT places input data.

- **Scenario library population.** The scenario library should be both large enough and contain scenarios involving time series of environmental variables that differ in both intensity and duration. In this way, the EWS System will be able to associate the examined event at certain occurrence probability with the scenarios present in the library and then recognize at what extent the event is dangerous or not. This phase of calibration has been fundamental in the EWS implementation and performance assessment. The types of scenarios included in the library are described in detail. It is specified that these scenarios contain the files with the time series used as input for this scenario. These include the rainfall intensity pattern (mm/h), sea state (m a.s.l.) and river state (m³/s). The scenario also includes a copy of the bathymetry, the EBAs polygons used (if any) and the risk maps for area population density, building repair cost and road repair cost. These maps are used to calculate the level of damage based on the maximum height reached by water. Finally, the scenario includes the output files of the simulation, namely the maps of the maximum water height and the maps returned by the DT-USE for the event corresponding to the time series of environmental variables.
- **Real scenarios.** More than 15 ordinary rainfall events were selected to affect the CCLLs area. The time series of environmental variables were processed as described above and the scenarios were inserted into the library.
- **Synthetic scenarios.** Synthetic scenarios have been created based on the series of rainfall intensity and triangular hydrographs corresponding to 20, 30, 200, 500-year return periods (RPs). Additional synthetic time series of environmental variables have been created using predefined values, with the aim of generating flooding scenarios with a lower flood extent compared to those associated with high RPs.

6.3.1 Validation of EWS to flood events in Marina di Massa

From the local news and the reports provided both by the municipalities and the Civil Protection, three historical events of intense precipitation or flooding have been identified. These events had likewise prompted warnings from the Civil Protection authorities, although these were issued only at the provincial or regional levels. In addition, a synthetic scenario has been created starting from the real event of 21.10.2013. In particular, the duration of the precipitation peak in the time series of rainfall intensity has been extended. The plots of these historical events are reported below. These plots are divided into three parts:

- A histogram that, for the duration of the analyzed event, represents the probability of occurrence of the analyzed event associated with the scenarios present in the library. The scenarios of the library to which a higher probability of occurrence has been associated are represented and listed in the legend.
- A point graph representing the evolution of the prevailing scenario: the scenario of the library to which the highest probability of occurrence has been associated with each iteration.
- The time series of rainfall intensity and river flow over the duration of the event analyzed.

The alarm, depicted as a red band with a length corresponding to its duration, is shown in all three sections of the plots from Figure 11 to Figure 14.

It is observed that, across all four validation scenarios, the EWS System consistently demonstrates its ability to detect potential flood risk based on the time series of rainfall intensity and river flow. In each case, the alarm was activated in advance—before the rainfall and/or river flow values reached their respective peaks. This capability is especially evident and can be observed especially in the real events shown in Figure 11, 12, and 13. Within the precipitation time series, rainfall intensity increases sharply over a short period, quickly reaching its peak value. This behavior is

characteristic of the most intense precipitation events. The DT-EWS proves to be effective in the recognition of these events thanks to its ability to frequently update the computation of the probability of occurrence associated with the different scenarios present in the library (every frequent time-steps (30 min)). Specifically, in relation to the event of November 2012 represented in Figure 11, it can be clearly observed that the alarm precedes the different peaks reached first by the values of precipitation intensity and then by the river discharge values.

Such a sudden change in rainfall intensity values over a short time period results in a rapid change in the likelihood of the current scenario in relation to the scenarios in the EWS library. The synthetic scenario represented in Figure 14 exhibited a similar trend. Thus, it is observed that DT-EWS manages to effectively assimilate the information provided by the temporal evolution of the environmental variables monitored through the integrated real-time sensors, even in the presence of intense precipitation events. In addition, the system's ability to recognize risks and prompt trigger alerts can be attributed to the design of the scenario library that underpins the EWS.

This effectiveness of risk recognition and promptness in triggering the alert is attributable to the structure of the scenario library on which the EWS is based. It is observed that, in the time steps coinciding with the warning phase, the scenario associated with a higher probability of occurrence alternates intermittently between a real scenario (as for the scenario R_2021-09-17 of Figure 13) and sometimes a synthetic scenario (as for the S_constant_RF80_PR10 scenario in Figure 11). This indicates that it can therefore be stated that the EWS library of scenarios is properly calibrated.

In conclusion, the ability of DT-EWS to promptly recognize dangerous situations highlights the system's effectiveness in real-time monitoring and early warning.

These results support the conclusion that the EWS not only works reliably under diverse conditions but also serves as a crucial tool in proactive emergency management. Its capacity to provide timely alerts based on evolving environmental data significantly reduces response time and contributes to mitigating the impacts of flood events.

Figure 11. Analysis of the 11 November 2012 real event in Marina di Massa. The plot shows the occurrence probability associated with the scenarios in the library and the time series of rainfall intensity and river flow of the real event analysed.

Figure 12. Analysis of the 05 November 2014 real even in Marina di Massa. The plot shows the occurrence probability associated with the scenarios in the library and the time series of rainfall intensity and river flow of the examined real event analysed.

Figure 13. Analysis of the 19 November 2023 real event in Marina di Massa. The plot shows the occurrence probability associated with the scenarios in the library and the time series of rainfall intensity and river flow of the examined real event analysed.

Figure 14. Analysis of a synthetic event based on the 21 October 2013 real event in Marina di Massa. The plot shows the occurrence probability associated with the scenarios in the library and the time series of rainfall intensity and river flow of the examined real event analysed.

6.3.2 Validation of EWS to flood events in Oarsoaldea

From the local news, two historical events of intense precipitation and flooding have been identified. The first flooding event affected Oarsoaldea on 19 May 2019 and it was previously used for the validation of DT-USE. The second event occurred on 10 December 2021. In addition, a synthetic scenario has been created starting from the real event of 24 January 2019. In particular, the river discharge and the rainfall intensity values have been amplified to obtain time series that reproduce an extreme event. The plots of these validation events are shown in Figure 15-17 and divided into three parts:

- A histogram that, for the duration of the analyzed event, represents the probability of occurrence of the analyzed event associated with the scenarios present in the library. The scenarios of the library with which a higher probability of occurrence has been associated are represented and listed in the legend.

- A point graph representing the evolution of the prevailing scenario: the scenario of the library to which the highest probability of occurrence has been associated with each iteration.
- The time series of rainfall intensity and river flow over the duration of the event was analyzed.

The alarm, depicted as a red band with a length corresponding to its duration, is shown in all three sections of the plots from Figure 15 to Figure 17.

Observing the plots of Figure 15 and Figure 16 provides similar considerations to those reported in the validation of the DT-EWS of Marina di Massa. Analysis across the validation scenarios confirms that the EWS System consistently demonstrates reliable performance in identifying potential flood risk based on the time series of rainfall intensity and river discharge. In each case, the alarm was triggered in advance of the peak values of the river flow. In both real events represented in plots of Figure 15 and Figure 16, it is evident that the system exhibits greater sensitivity to flood risk recognition associated with river discharge as the alert is issued before the peak in river discharge, rather than before the peak in precipitation intensity. This is an advantage in the case of the Oarsoaldea CCLL, where the Oiartzun river plays a major role in the flooding risk. The synthetic scenario in Figure 17 was created to challenge the EWS system for extreme events. It is observed that also in this case the system promptly detects the alarm at the beginning of the scenario when the river discharge is at its maximum. The alarm is then reactivated when the flow rate of the river continues to grow until it reaches a further peak.

In conclusion, the EWS System's ability to promptly identify hazardous conditions underscores its effectiveness in real-time monitoring and early warning. The findings from these test events confirm that the EWS operates reliably across a range of scenarios, both real and synthetic ones, and represents an important component of proactive flood risk management. Its capability to issue timely alerts based on continuously updated environmental data plays a key role in reducing response times and minimizing the impacts of flood events.

Figure 15. Analysis of the 19 May 2019 real event in Oarsoaldea. The plot shows the occurrence probability associated with the scenarios in the library and the time series of rainfall intensity and river flow of the examined real event analysed.

Figure 16. Analysis of the 10 December 2021 real event. The plot shows the occurrence probability associated with the scenarios in the library and the time series of rainfall intensity and river flow of the examined real event analysed.

Figure 17. Analysis of a synthetic event based on the 24 January 2019 real event in Oarsoaldea. The plot shows the occurrence probability associated with the scenarios in the library and the time series of rainfall intensity and river flow of the examined real event analysed.

7 USABILITY ASSESSMENT

To evaluate the usability, user experience, and interactions with the DT-EWS system, we concentrate on usability testing. According to an ISO standard definition, usability testing assesses the effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction with which users accomplish specific goals in a given context [R53][R54].

The usability tests for the SCORE DT-EWS involved small groups of end-users with different roles in their CLLs. Participants are requested to perform a series of routine tasks that align with different operational flows and interactions with the system's data outputs and visualizations. Various use cases and end-users will be selected for both the DT and the EWS. The goal of these tests is to assess how users interact with and experience the GIS-based GUI, identifying any issues or difficulties.

The user interface of the SCORE DT-EWS is described in the specific deliverables SCORE D8.6 – Tools to access and visualise SCORE data and outcomes [R13] and SCORE D8.7 – Tools to access and visualize SCORE data and outcomes release notes [R14].

The expected users were different for the USE and EWS subsystems. USE, in principle, could be used by the general public. However, a minimum of training is required and moreover, the current demonstrator can handle only one instance at a time. Therefore, the usability tests were conducted with the same team that took part in the System presentation and tutorial and the User-feedback session (section 5). The usability tests were planned to be conducted between the months 27 and 36 of the SCORE project. However, several delays in the deployment and in tuning the system have forced us to allocate the last user-feedback session in month 47 (i.e. 30 May 2025), although most of the work concerning usability was conducted and accomplished in Massa until M39 (September 2024).

In the user-feedback sessions, a questionnaire was delivered that contained specific inquiries concerning the usability of the systems and effectiveness of output.

DT-EWS has a web-based interface designed to support end-users in visualizing data from the SCORE ICT Platform (SIP), live sensor feeds, and publicly available geospatial sources such as Copernicus. Data access is facilitated through RESTful APIs, ensuring users interact with the system via a secure and scalable data service layer rather than directly with the SIP backend. The DT-EWS platform is developed using the Django web framework, which manages backend logic, URL routing, and data preprocessing. It operates in conjunction with Gunicorn and Nginx to optimize server performance and data delivery.

The front end is enhanced using modern web technologies, including a) Tailwind CSS and Flowbite for responsive and modular UI design; JavaScript and Axios for asynchronous communication with backend APIs; Flowbite Django UI for integrating interactive components within Django-based projects. These tools collectively support full CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations, particularly within the User Scenario Evaluation (USE) interface.

The system adheres to Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards, supporting protocols such as WMS, WFS, and WMTS for accessing geographic data [R21].

The TerriaJS platform is employed for catalog exploration and visualization, and integrating:

- Leaflet for 2D interactive mapping.
- CesiumJS for 3D geospatial visualization.
- React for building modular, component-based user interfaces.

The use of open-source technologies ensures that the DT-EWS interface is both scalable and reusable across different deployment contexts. Its modular architecture allows for the integration of additional data sources and functionalities, supporting long-term adaptability and user-centered development.

From the point of view of usability assessment, the focus was on the input/output of USE and output of EWS. It should be noted that specifications of interface were provided in D8.2 [R9] and verified in D8.5 [R12].

The USE interface component provides the necessary tools for the creation and configuration of simulation scenarios. Any scenario in the interface can be described using the factors, ID, Name, Description Baseline map ID, and List of ID of changes to the baseline map. Scenarios are created through a proper configuration tool that provides the user with the EBAs and their description selectable from a palette. Location of EBA can be selected by a polygon editor that allows the user to draw the area in which the EBA should be implemented. Maximum simulation time can be also set (in the order of minutes). Within the USE interface, users can configure simulation scenarios by selecting or entering parameters through a dedicated Parameters Editor. This includes:

- **Simulation Duration and Timing:** Users define the total duration and specify start/end times for simulation intervals.
- **Sea State:** Selection from predefined categories representing coastal and marine conditions.
- **Hydrographical Conditions:** Input of river and canal flow rates (m^3/s) per timeslot, or selection from historical presets based on return periods or future climate scenarios (e.g., RCP4.5, RCP8.5).
- **Weather Conditions:** Selection of predefined weather events or manual input of rainfall rates (mm/h) across time intervals.

This setup enables detailed, scenario-specific digital twin simulations within the defined simulation boundary.

In the users' feedback session, users involved in the validation smooth the editing procedure, which, indeed, is like a procedure used in GIS and users involved in usability testing are used to GIS software. The possibility of importing e.g., time series of river discharge and rainfall from an external source was requested. In fact, a manual input is considered cumbersome for running several simulations (especially if future versions of ET-EWS will allow multiple simulations in parallel).

The output of the system pertains more to usefulness than usability. The USE output is provided as animation, and/or pdf including mapping of, Maximum level of Water, and Risk. Such maps can be visualized also through the DT-EWS interface. Feedback received, concerned reporting not only the maximum water level, but also a temporal evolution, and obtain differentiated outputs for users.

About EWS, the process is running in the background, and outputs are in the form of alarm and associated duration, and probabilities. Feedback was lacking on this because users' involved were not occupationally involved in issuing alarm, which instead mostly was provided by external bodies, such weather services. However, the suggestions concerning the possibility of sending warnings to specific segments of users (e.g. schools) expressed in Vilanova, have been collected.

In fact, EWS runs automatically and most of the interest of users was in the output produced, as in contrast to interaction between humans and the system.

Suggestions about the output were collected through a questionnaire (see 11APPENDIX A) that contains specific questions on this aspect.

Some of the findings summarized above are derived from the answers to these questionnaires:

- Which of the figures should receive EWS module alert messages?

- In what context might the EWS module alert messages arrive?
- Who will be the authorized user to first use and test the system?
- Every 15', the EWS gives as output of the most probable scenario. If there is at least one in the associated maps where a cell exceeds the alert threshold, the alert is triggered.
 - Does an output every 15' minutes provide a sufficiently accurate frequency?
 - What time horizon may be sufficient (3h, 6h...)?
 - How to establish alarm thresholds? Starting from how many people might be affected? Or, as of what magnitude of economic damage?
- If there are areas of the city that require special attention, which areas should be considered? As of what level of flooding?
 - Do you prefer danger bands hazard-prone zones (e.g., yellow/orange/red/black alert)?
 - Should the system keep in memory some past hazard maps, even if the time to which they refer has already passed?
- At the end of the simulations, the USE module outputs a PDF report that summarizes the main data of the simulation and its results. Based on this report, the user can determine whether the results obtained can be further studied or discarded. Do users find the report useful? Can such propose system be improved, e.g., further pieces of information that could be added to the report?
- At the end of the simulations, the USE module gives output flood and damage maps. Do you think only the final maps are necessary, (i.e., related to the simulation's final instant), or are also the intermediate ones helpful?

8 IMPACT ASSESSMENT

The implementation of SCORE's DT-EWS is expected to significantly impact on co-design practices and co-warning processes for SCORE's CCLLs and external stakeholders. The methodology to assess the expected impact was outlined in SCORE D8.10 – Early-Warning and Spatial Digital Twin Assessment Plan [R17], (section 9). It was tailored to the WP8 frontrunners (Massa, Oarsoaldea and Vilanova) and the WP8 followers (Sligo, Dublin, Benidorm, Oeiras, Gdansk, Samsun, and Piran) and heavily relies on CCLLs activities to be carried out through WP2 and WP9.

The SCORE Knowledge Transfer process has been carried out as part of WP9 within the impact assessment framework to identify slightly different target users and pathways to impact mainly through a business perspective, identified with the assistance of the advisory board and the SCORE Innovation Board. The process aimed to evaluate the technology's impact while ensuring its benefits extend beyond the project's duration, including frontrunner CCLLs that had the opportunity to deploy the DT and EWS locally and the and the fellow CCLLs that had at disposal presentation without the opportunity to interact with the system along the project.

Frontrunner Methodology: Feedback for impact assessment from frontrunners was collected mainly at the meetings described and reported in section 4.34.3. Scheduling of the meetings reflected the advancement of the development and tuning activity conducted by MBI until the end of May 2025 (last event in Oarsoaldea). The dates differed for each frontrunner to allow flexibility for key target stakeholders (the process started with Massa). Using feedback and reports from those meeting and analysis of the questionnaires developed by Knowledge Transfer partners from ERINN, ERINN developed tailored Knowledge Transfer Plans (KTPs) for the DT-EWS for each frontrunner location using the Knowledge Transfer methodology outlined in the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of the Project Results (D9.1) [R55][R55]. The development of the KTPs was supported by the Innovation Manager and wider Innovation Board, comprised of all SCORE partner SMEs. The impact assessments, and corresponding KTPs, include Impact Readiness Indicators, called Impact Readiness Levels (IRL) [R56][R57][R57]. The IRLs can be mapped to the more widely recognized Technology Readiness Levels and Societal Readiness Levels for comparison. Results of this work were consolidated in the SCORE D9.3 – Final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities [R18].

Follower methodology: The KTP for frontrunners was presented to the fellow CCLLs at the final CCLL Board Meeting in 2025, allowing the Impact Assessment team to both ensure knowledge transfer within the project and to gain the fellows perspectives and feedback on the potential application and impact of these technologies for their locality. Fellows had the opportunity to hear from frontrunners on their experiences with the DT-EWS and insights on how deployment took place in their specific contexts. Following this interactive session, KTPs were finalised for each of the fellow CCLLs to support future/potential uptake of DT-EWS in their region. These two actions allowed the fellows to not only gain an understanding of the developed technologies within WP8, but to begin the process of identifying opportunities for this technology to be used within their local context.

Throughout the process, the continuous monitoring and evaluation of the impact and effectiveness of the SCORE DT/USE and EWS systems allowed for the utilised impact assessment methodology to be iterated based on feedback and lessons learned.

The methodology enabled the evaluation of SCORE technologies not only in terms of their technical deployment but also in relation to their contribution to the co-design processes, stakeholder collaboration, and capacity building. The impact assessment emphasized how the DT and EWS supported institutional learning, data-driven planning, and

climate resilience in the pilot cities. Special attention was given to the frontrunner CCLs, as they were actively involved in deploying and embedding these tools within local governance and decision-making processes.

Feedback sessions with the frontrunner CCLs contributed to the impact analysis by providing insight into how DT-EWS influenced strategic planning, stakeholder engagement, and risk preparedness. Responses were analyzed not only to refine the tools but also to understand how their implementation advanced key SCORE objectives, such as knowledge exchange, adaptive capacity, and systemic innovation.

Moreover, the impact assessment benefited from real-world validation scenarios. The involvement of CCLs in identifying flooding events, selecting in-situ sensors, and contributing territorial data (such as DEMs) allowed the EWS to be calibrated with actual conditions. These efforts enhanced the credibility of the technologies and demonstrated their capacity to support evidence-based decision-making—key criteria in the project's long-term impact strategy.

The subsection report and summarize specific feedback concerning assessment impact gathered from meetings and events organized at CCLs concerning impact on local government involved.

8.1 Frontrunner CCLs feedback on DT-EWS impact

In the frontrunners cities, after giving users a few weeks to familiarize themselves with the system, a feedback session was held. During this session, users shared their comments and observations, which provided valuable insights for improving the system. Overall, the response was positive, with users expressing general satisfaction and offering suggestions for future enhancements—such as including additional information related to the EBAs in the GUI. Users were invited to respond to a series of questions aimed at evaluating the long-term viability of these systems in relation to their professional activities, identifying areas for improvement, and ensuring their overall usability and effectiveness. This input was essential for gathering interest in the system, its novelty, and its role in implementing duties of administration. Furthermore, it was also supportive of shaping future versions of the system and guiding best practices for adoption by key stakeholders. The Italian and Spanish versions used at the CCLs are included in Appendix A, while a commented summary in English can be found in section 4.3.

8.1.1 Summary of Massa feedback on DT-EWS impact

The SCORE DT-USE and EWS survey conducted in Massa, Italy, involved a Public Works Engineer and other technical and administrative officers from the municipality (3 respondents). Respondents generally expressed a positive outlook on the potential of DT, considering it as intuitive and manageable for trained technicians, capable of making planning and prevention more efficient and targeted by simulating various risk scenarios against historical data. While some found the integration "difficult" and workload "increased," they believed the benefits, such as enhanced situational awareness and support for designing EBAs, justified its use. Current EWS usage in Massa's municipality was noted as manual, with a desire for more advanced systems that could leverage real-time data. Potential users identified were the Civil Protection Office, Public Works, and Planning departments, as well as those responsible for infrastructure maintenance (sewers, canals), with the understanding that data interpretation must be handled by qualified personnel due to its sensitive nature. All Massa respondents indicated they would continue using both the DT and EWS if accessible, highlighting the need for continuous training, an updated base map (requiring collaboration between users and developers), and a clear understanding of confidentiality, especially regarding sensitive data and potential compensation claims.

8.1.2 Summary of Vilanova i la Geltrù feedback on DT-EWS impact

The SCORE DT-USE and EWS survey, conducted in Vilanova i la Geltrú, Barcelona, gathered feedback from municipal technicians, researchers, and academics (4 respondents) on the systems viability, usability, and opportunities for enhancement.

While respondents varied in their familiarity with Digital Twins and current EWS usage (some employing manual or weather-based systems, others none), all recognized the value of the DT for improved decision-making, planning, and situational awareness. However, participants noted challenges in system integration, with some finding it difficult and requiring intermediate expert experience, potentially adding to workloads.

Typical users identified include politicians, technicians, civil protection, and city planners. While the system design was generally considered logical, some feedback pointed to complexity and access issues, highlighting the need for continued support, budget, and maintenance.

Despite these concerns, all respondents indicated they would continue to use the DT-EWS if given access, emphasizing the necessity of expert and trained personnel for its effective implementation and its potential for public utilization if properly disseminated.

8.1.3 Summary of Oarsoaldea feedback on DT-EWS impact

Participants in the survey hold various roles, such as sustainability technicians, urban regeneration managers, and ecological coordinators (6 respondents). They represent both public institutions, working at municipal, regional, and comarca levels, and private sector organizations like consultancies.

All respondents reported that their municipality or region currently uses some form of early warning system, most commonly meteorological alerts and flood warnings. When asked about the usability of the new system being evaluated, most found the design logical and intuitive, with several describing it as "very logical and intuitive." While a few respondents noted that improvements could be made, the overall feedback was positive and constructive.

Looking ahead, participants expressed a range of expectations for how they might use the digital twin system in the future. Some envisioned it as a planning tool or a way to engage citizens, while others saw it supporting local government decision-making or simulating the effects of ecosystem-based adaptation (EBA) strategies. There was a general consensus that the results produced by the system could be accessible to the public, though a few noted that efforts might be needed to simplify the outputs for broader understanding.

When it came to confidentiality, most respondents either said they were unsure or didn't identify specific concerns. As for the likelihood of continued use, the majority expressed a willingness to keep using the digital twin or the early warning system if given access. Overall, the feedback reflects a constructive and optimistic view of the system's potential, both in professional planning and in broader community engagement.

8.2 DT-EWS Impact Assessment survey key insights

The provided documents contain feedback from 13 surveys responses on SCORE's DT and USE. These systems are designed to assist in flood risk projection and analysis for coastal cities. The surveys aimed to gather insights on the systems' viability, potential enhancements, usability, and effectiveness to inform future development and adoption by key users in areas such as Vilanova i la Geltrú, Barcelona, Spain, and Massa, Italy.

Key Findings from the Surveys:

- **System Purpose:**
 - The **Digital Twin (DT) User Scenario Evaluation (USE) subsystem** enables "what-if" simulations and long-term analyses by combining real-world urban data with hypothetical inputs (e.g., weather, sea conditions, Environment-based Actions).
 - The **Early Warning Support (EWS) subsystem** uses real-time sensor data and weather forecasts to project flood risk and can issue alerts to complement existing warning mechanisms.
- **Respondent Profiles and Current Practices:**
 - Participants included a diverse group of professionals such as researchers/lecturers, academics, municipal environmental technicians, technical environmental experts, urban ecology coordinators, technical architects, public works engineers, deputy heads of civil protection, and technical geologists.
 - Current early warning systems in use vary; some municipalities have manual systems, others use meteorological and flood alerts, while some do not have an Early Warning System.
 - Familiarity with Digital Twins ranged, with some using similar tools like GIS.
- **Perceived Value and Benefits:**
 - Respondents see the Digital Twin as a valuable tool to complement or potentially replace existing solutions.
 - Benefits include improved data analysis for interventions and infrastructure maintenance, and enabling more informed planning and design for public and environmental safety.
 - The Digital Twin is envisioned for simulating various risk scenarios, comparing them with historical data, and supporting civil protection, public works, and planning offices. It could also generate alerts for marine weather.
 - If properly disseminated, the Digital Twin's results could be utilized by the general public.
 - The Early Warning Support System is seen as useful for prevention, hydraulic works, infrastructure maintenance, and civil protection.
 - Potential users identified for both systems include civil protection, city planners, politicians, technicians, citizens, marine weather observers, and departments responsible for infrastructure maintenance (e.g., Municipality of Massa, Public Works, Civil Protection, Environment).
 - Most respondents indicated they would continue using both systems if given access.
- **Challenges and Considerations:**

- Integrating the systems into current workflows is anticipated to be between "not difficult" and "moderately difficult."
- The realism of user adoption is generally positive, with some finding it "very realistic."
- Operation of the systems would require varying levels of expertise, from basic to expert, suggesting a need for trained technical personnel.
- Confidentiality considerations include elements related to compensation and the necessity of qualified personnel to interpret sensitive data and assess its impact. However, some respondents stated no confidentiality concerns for their open-access tools.
- The systems are generally perceived as intuitive and manageable for trained technicians, promoting more conscious planning.
- Continuous maintenance and updates of base mapping are deemed crucial, requiring collaboration between users and developers.
- The overall design of the system was considered logical and intuitive by most participants.

8.3 Follower CCLLs feedbacks

After the final assessment meeting with frontrunners, considering relevant experience carried out at the three frontrunners, DT-EWS and KTPs were presented to the fellow CCLLs during the *"WP8 SCORE-CCLL board meeting: Digital Twin Knowledge transfer and learning exchanges"* held online on June 6, 2025. The meeting included also updates from other WPs, like the status of citizen science sensors of WP4 and their interface with the SCORE ICT platform (SIP) and updates on financial strategies developed in WP6.

In this occasion, after an explanation of the work and outputs developed by MBI and CNR, the floor was given to frontrunners to hear their experience and expectations followed by an open discussion. Further, this allowed the Impact Assessment team to facilitate knowledge transfer within the project and gather feedback from the fellows on the potential application and impact of the technologies in their localities.

Unfortunately, the actual implementation of the project did not allow SCORE to plan further installations in one or more fellow CCLLs. The fact that there were requests from followers for testing the DT-EWS application somehow certifies the attractiveness of the tool. This is part of the planning of DT-EWS after SCORE completion. In addition to finding new project opportunities to further develop the product, MBI has secured at least one year of access to the DT-EWS server to SCORE team. However, the lack of technical skills at most CCLLs make problematic new installations. A further request from forerunners was to include different simulations, such heath waves of diffusion of pollutants. The architecture of DT-EWS is quite flexible and implementing different new modelling should not be so difficult, but is certainly not straightforward. For example, the DT-EWS relies on historical local data that are likely available only at local level and need some adaptation/interface work to be used in the DT-EWS.

Following this interactive session, KTPs and stakeholder engagement plans were finalised for each of the fellow CCLLs to support the future adoption of the DT-EWS in their regions. These actions enabled the fellows to not only understand the technologies developed within WP8 but also begin identifying opportunities for their application within their local contexts [R18].

9 REFERENCES

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10 APPENDIX A: QUESTIONNAIRES

Below we list the Italian and Spanish versions of the Digital Twin and Early Warning Support System Feedback Questionnaires.

10.1 Italian version

(used in Massa, first time on 20 Settembre 2024)

Indagine sugli utenti del Digital Twin e del sistema di supporto all'allertamento SCORE

Vi ringraziamo per aver partecipato a questa sessione di raccolta feedback sul Digital Twin e sul Sistema di Supporto all'Allerta Precoce di SCORE.

Questo sondaggio mira a raccogliere le vostre opinioni su due componenti chiave: il Digital Twin (DT) User Scenario Evaluation (USE) e l'Early Warning Support System (EWS).

Il sottosistema Digital Twin - User Scenario Evaluation (USE) consente agli utenti di effettuare simulazioni di scenari "what-if" e analisi a lungo termine, combinando dati reali di una città costiera con input ipotetici, come eventi meteorologici, condizioni del mare e azioni basate sull'ambiente (EBA) applicate all'interno dell'area di studio urbana.

Il sottosistema Early Warning Support utilizza i dati dei sensori in tempo reale e le previsioni meteorologiche per proiettare il rischio di alluvione della città. Questo sistema può emettere avvisi e integrarsi con i meccanismi di allerta precoce esistenti.

Questo sondaggio analizzerà le vostre opinioni sulla possibilità di inserire questi sistemi nella vostra linea di lavoro, individuerà le opportunità di miglioramento e ne garantirà l'usabilità e l'efficacia. Il vostro riscontro avrà un ruolo cruciale nel definire le future versioni di questi sistemi e nel guidare le migliori pratiche per la loro adozione da parte degli utenti chiave di Massa.

Fattori demografici:

1. Qual è il suo ruolo?
2. Se è un funzionario pubblico, a quale livello opera?
 - Comunale
 - Regionale
 - Nazionale
 - [Altro (specificare): _____]

Esperienza attuale con sistemi Digital Twin e sistemi di supporto all'allertamento

- Il vostro comune (o la vostra regione) utilizza attualmente un sistema di allerta precoce (early warning)?
 - Sì
 - No
- Quali sistemi di allerta precoce utilizzate attualmente? (Selezionare tutte le risposte pertinenti)
 - Allerte meteorologico
 - Allerte sismiche
 - Allarme idrogeologico
 - Altro (specificare): _____
- Esistono strumenti simili che utilizzate abitualmente per scopi analoghi sistema di supporto all'allertamento di SCORE (EWS)? (risposta aperta)
- Avete già utilizzato uno strumento Digital Twin prima d'ora?
 - Sì
 - No
- Avete familiarità con il concetto di Digital Twin ?
(Scala - da 1 nessuna familiarità a 5 molta familiarità)

- Esistono strumenti che utilizzate abitualmente per scopi simili al Digital Twin di SCORE? (risposta aperta)
- Un Digital Twin come quello di SCORE twin si presta a sostituire uno strumento già esistente o è uno strumento nuovo di cui si sentiva la mancanza? (Risposta Aperta)

Motivazioni per l'Utilizzo di uno strumento Digital Twin:

3. Trova proficuo l'utilizzo di un Digital Twin ? (Risposta aperta)
- Se la risposta è positiva, per, per quali dei seguenti obiettivi?
 - Miglioramento del processo decisionale
 - Migliore pianificazione
 - Analisi più rapide
 - Maggiore consapevolezza della situazione
 - Altro (specificare): _____

Integrazione del Digital Twin SCORE con sistemi esistenti:

12. Quanto ritenete difficile integrare il sistema SCORE con i sistemi esistenti?

[] Molto difficile - [] Piuttosto difficile - [] Neutro - [] Piuttosto facile - [] Molto facile

- Quanto è realistico che gli utenti possano utilizzare questo servizio (o servizi simili)?
 - Non realistico
 - Piuttosto realistico
 - Molto realistico
- Quale livello di esperienza ritenete necessario per utilizzare il sistema?
 - Principiante
 - Intermedio
 - Esperto
- 13. Quale sarebbe l'utente tipo di questo sistema nella vostra zona? (risposta aperta)
- 14. Questo strumento alleggerisce o aumenta il carico di lavoro?
 - Alleggerisce il carico di lavoro
 - Aumenta il carico di lavoro
 - Neutro
- Con quale frequenza potrebbe essere usato questo strumento?
 - Raramente
 - Occasionalmente
 - Frequentemente
- Quanto sono aperti gli utenti a questo tipo di nuova tecnologia/servizio?
 - Molto aperti
 - Abbastanza aperti
 - Neutro
 - Piuttosto resistenti
 - Molto resistente
- Di che tipo di supporto avreste bisogno per utilizzare questo strumento nel vostro ufficio?
 - Considerazioni sul budget
 - supporto tecnologico
 - manutenzione
 - Altro

Progettazione del sistema:

15. Trovate il sistema progettato per un uso logico e intuitivo?
- Molto logico e intuitivo

- Abbastanza logico e intuitivo
- Neutro
- Piuttosto illogico e poco intuitivo
- Molto illogico e poco intuitivo

16. Altri commenti sul design del sistema? (risposta aperta)

- Valutare la complessità del sistema:
 - Troppo semplice
 - Giusta
 - Troppo complessa

Utilità dei risultati:

- Come immagina di utilizzare questo Digital Twin in futuro? (risposta aperta)
17. I risultati forniti dal Digital Twin potrebbero essere tradotti per essere utilizzati nella vostra zona ? (risposta aperta)
18. Può immaginare che il suo dipartimento utilizzi il Sistema di supporto all'allerta precoce in futuro? (risposta aperta)
19. Chi potrebbero essere i potenziali utenti dei risultati del Digital Twin o del Sistema di allerta precoce EWS ? (risposta aperta)
- Quali elementi di riservatezza e confidenzialità dovrebbero essere considerati per utilizzare questo sistema ? (risposta aperta)

Altri commenti:

Sentitevi liberi di condividere qualsiasi ulteriore pensiero o commento. (Risposta aperta)

Se avesse accesso a questo strumento oltre SCORE, continuerebbe a utilizzare il gemello digitale e/o il sistema di supporto all'allertamento? (Risposta aperta)

Conformità con il GDPR

I partner del progetto SCORE sono soggetti al Regolamento generale sulla protezione dei dati dell'UE (GDPR). I dati raccolti ed elaborati ai fini di questo esercizio sono pertanto soggetti al GDPR. Per poter utilizzare le vostre risposte al presente questionario, abbiamo bisogno del vostro consenso al trattamento dei vostri dati. Si prega di spuntare la casella per confermare il proprio consenso.

10.2 Spanish version

(used in Vilanova I la Geltrú and in Oarsoaldea)

Digital Twin and Early Warning Support System Survey

Gracias por participar en este formulario de valoración del Gemelo Digital y Sistema de Apoyo de Alerta Temprana de SCORE.

Esta encuesta busca recopilar sus opiniones sobre dos componentes clave: la Evaluación de Escenarios de Usuario (USE, por sus siglas en inglés: *User Scenario Evaluation*) del Gemelo Digital (DT, por sus siglas en inglés: *Digital Twin*) y el Sistema de Apoyo de Alerta Temprana (EWSS, por sus siglas en inglés: *Early Warning Support System*). Estos dos sistemas:

- El subsistema de Evaluación de Escenarios de Usuario del Gemelo Digital (USE) permite a los usuarios realizar simulaciones para escenarios «*what-if*» y análisis de largo plazo, combinando datos del mundo real de una ciudad costera con datos de entrada o *inputs* hipotéticos, como fenómenos meteorológicos, condiciones del mar y Adaptaciones basadas en los Ecosistemas (AbEs) aplicadas dentro de la zona urbana de estudio.
- El subsistema de Apoyo de Alerta Temprana utiliza datos de sensores en tiempo real y previsiones meteorológicas para proyectar el riesgo de inundación de la ciudad. Este sistema puede emitir alertas para complementar los mecanismos de alerta temprana existentes.

Esta encuesta evaluará sus opiniones sobre la viabilidad a largo plazo de estos sistemas en su línea de trabajo, identificará oportunidades de mejora, y busca garantizar su usabilidad y eficacia. Sus comentarios son fundamentales para dar forma a las futuras versiones de estos sistemas y guiar la creación de mejores prácticas para facilitar su implementación por parte de los usuarios clave de _____.

Factores demográficos:

1. ¿Cuál es su cargo?
2. Si es funcionario, ¿a qué nivel trabaja?
 - Municipal
 - Regional
 - Nacional
 - [Otro (especifique): _____]

Experiencia actual con DT y EWS

3. ¿Su municipio (o región) utiliza actualmente un Sistema de Alerta Temprana?
 - Sí
 - No
4. ¿Qué sistemas de alerta temprana utiliza actualmente? (Seleccione todos los que procedan)
 - Alertas meteorológicas
 - Alertas sísmicas
 - Alertas por inundaciones
 - Otros (especifique): _____
- ¿Existen herramientas similares que suele utilizar para fines parecidos a los del sistema de apoyo a la alerta temprana? (Pregunta abierta)
5. ¿Ha utilizado antes un Gemelo Digital?
 - Sí
 - No
6. ¿Está familiarizado con el concepto de Gemelos Digitales? (Escala - 1 No familiarizado a 5 muy familiarizado)
7. ¿Existe(n) alguna(s) herramienta(s) similar(es) que utilice habitualmente para fines parecidos al Gemelo Digital de SCORE? (Pregunta abierta)

- ¿El sistema de Gemelos Digitales sustituye a una herramienta existente o atiende a una necesidad no cubierta? (Pregunta abierta)

Motivación para utilizar un Gemelo Digital:

8. ¿Encuentra valor en usar un Gemelo Digital? (Pregunta abierta)
9. En caso afirmativo, ¿qué beneficios aporta un Gemelo Digital?
 - Una mejor toma de decisiones
 - Una mejor planificación
 - Análisis más rápidos
 - Mayor conocimiento de la situación
 - Otros (especifique): _____

Integración del Gemelo Digital con los sistemas existentes:

10. ¿En qué medida sería difícil integrar este sistema en sus sistemas actuales?
 - Muy difícil
 - Difícil
 - Neutro
 - Fácil
 - Muy fácil
11. ¿Es realista que los usuarios utilicen este servicio?
 - No es realista
 - Realista
 - Muy realista
- ¿Qué nivel de experiencia cree que necesitaría alguien para utilizar el sistema?
 - Principiante
 - Intermedio
 - Experto
12. ¿Quién sería el usuario tipo del sistema en su caso? (Pregunta abierta)
13. ¿Esta herramienta aligera o aumenta su carga de trabajo?
 - Aligera la carga de trabajo
 - Aumenta la carga de trabajo
 - Neutral
14. ¿Con qué frecuencia emplearía esta herramienta en su departamento?
 - Rara vez
 - Ocasionalmente
 - Frecuentemente
15. ¿Cómo de abiertos están los usuarios a este tipo de tecnología/servicio?
 - Muy abiertos
 - Abiertos
 - Neutral
 - Algo resistentes
 - Muy resistentes
16. ¿Qué apoyo necesitaría para utilizar esta herramienta en su departamento?
 - Consideraciones presupuestarias
 - Apoyo tecnológico

- Mantenimiento
- Otros

Diseño del sistema:

17. ¿Le ha parecido lógico e intuitivo el diseño del sistema?
- Muy lógico e intuitivo
 - Lógico e intuitivo
 - Neutral
 - Poco lógico e intuitivo
 - Muy poco lógico e intuitivo
18. ¿Algún comentario adicional sobre el diseño del sistema? (Pregunta abierta)
19. Valore la complejidad del sistema:
- Demasiado sencillo
 - Correcto
 - Demasiado complejo

Utilidad:

20. ¿Cómo imagina o prevé utilizar este Gemelo Digital en el futuro? (Pregunta abierta)
21. ¿Pueden los resultados de este Gemelo Digital ser traducidos/utilizados por el público en su localidad? (Pregunta abierta)
22. ¿Podría imaginarse a su departamento utilizando el Sistema de Apoyo a la Alerta Temprana en el futuro? (Pregunta abierta)
23. ¿Quiénes son los usuarios potenciales de los resultados del Gemelo Digital o del Sistema de Apoyo a la Alerta Temprana? (Pregunta abierta)
24. ¿Qué tipo de consideraciones de confidencialidad son necesarias? (Pregunta abierta)

Otros comentarios:

Siéntase libre de compartir aquí cualquier pensamiento o comentario adicional. (Pregunta abierta)

Si tuviera acceso a esto. ¿Continuaría utilizando el Gemelo Digital y/o el Sistema de Apoyo a la Alerta Temprana?

Cumplimiento del RGPD

Los socios del proyecto SCORE están sujetos al Reglamento General de Protección de Datos (RGPD) de la UE. Por lo tanto, los datos recopilados y procesados para este ejercicio están sujetos al RGPD. Para poder utilizar sus respuestas a este cuestionario, necesitamos su consentimiento para procesar sus datos. Marque la casilla para confirmar su consentimiento.

